

A Multi-Functional Heterogeneous Biocatalyst for the Oxygen-Free Oxidative Condensation of Primary Alcohols into β -Hydroxy Acids

Alejandro H. Orrego,^{1*} Idania L. López,¹ Daniel Andrés-Sanz,¹ Uxoá Fernández-Pelayo¹, Maialen Iturralde,¹ and Fernando López-Gallego^{1,2,*}

¹Center for Cooperative Research in Biomaterials (CIC biomaGUNE) – Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA). Paseo de Miramón, 182. 20014 Donostia-San Sebastián (Spain)

²Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science. Plaza Euskadi, 5. 48009. Bilbao (Spain)

*Corresponding authors: Fernando López-Gallego: flopez@cicbiomagune.es and Alejandro H. Orrego: aherrera@cicbiomagune.es

Abstract

Enantiomerically pure β -hydroxy acids are valuable building blocks in polymer and fine chemical industries. However, biosynthetic routes to these compounds are limited by narrow feedstock availability. Here, we report a confined, cell-free biosynthetic pathway that converts primary alcohols into β -hydroxy acids using a multifunctional heterogeneous biocatalyst. Five enzymes were co-immobilized and spatially organized on glyoxyl-functionalized porous supports: an alcohol dehydrogenase from *Bacillus stearothermophilus*, a truncated CoA-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica*, a thiolase from *Ralstonia eutropha*, a (S)-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase from *Thermus thermophilus* HB27, and a thioesterase from *E. coli*. The system efficiently transforms ethanol into (S)-3-hydroxybutyric acid, achieving 18 mM of product, a sevenfold yield increase over soluble enzymes (2.54 mM) through a design-build-test-learn (DBTL) approach. Enzyme confinement promotes optimal cofactor gradients, supporting redox balance and driving this thermodynamically unfavorable cascade. The biocatalyst exhibits broad substrate scope, converting esters, aldehydes, and diols (i.e., ethylene glycol, potentially derived from plastic waste) into β -hydroxy acids. Operated in a packed-bed flow reactor, it retained over 50% productivity after three weeks. This work advances in vitro biocatalytic cascades using immobilized enzymes to convert simple feedstocks into high-value chiral molecules.

1 Introduction

2 The synthesis of chiral molecules by biological processes has been
3 extensively investigated.^{1, 2} One example is the biosynthesis of hydroxyacids, a
4 family of versatile chiral molecules used as building blocks for the synthesis of
5 polymers and fine chemicals.³⁻⁷ Specifically, enantiomerically pure β -hydroxy
6 acids are the molecular bricks of industrially relevant biopolymers such as
7 poly(hydroxyalkanoates)⁸ and active pharmaceutical ingredients like the
8 cholesterol-lowering drug rosuvastatin.^{9, 10} Biosynthesis of 3-hydroxybutyric acid
9 (3-HBA) is among the most explored biotransformation targeting β -hydroxy
10 acids.^{3, 4, 11, 12} 3-HBA can also be chemically synthesized by either reducing ethyl
11 acetoacetate,¹³ or oxidizing 1,3-butanediol using metal catalysis.¹⁴ However,
12 these approaches generally exhibit reduced enantiomeric excess and
13 sustainability compared to biocatalytic routes. Alternatively, 3-HBA can be
14 obtained by depolymerization of poly(hydroxybutyrate)^{15, 16} (**Figure 1A**) or
15 transforming different carbon sources like bio-based sugars or small organic
16 acids using engineered microorganisms (**Figure 1B**).^{3, 5, 12} Latest advances in
17 metabolic and process engineering have boosted the titers of 3-hydroxybutyric
18 acid,^{3,5} as well as widened their chemical diversity by enabling the synthesis of
19 non-natural 3-hydroxy acids from glucose and/or organic acids.^{6, 17, 18} Beyond
20 glucose and small organic acids, (*S*)-3-HBA has been produced from ethanol
21 using engineered yeasts, yet using glucose as co-substrate to ensure an efficient
22 fed-batch process.¹⁹ Thus, an efficient biotransformation of ethanol as the sole
23 carbon source using engineered cells remains elusive.

24 As an alternative to engineered microbes, cell-free systems are gaining
25 relevance as toolboxes for developing more complex synthetic schemes and
26 applying them under non-physiological conditions.²⁰ Besides, enzyme
27 engineering enables the development of novel reactions that are not possible with
28 intact microbes, especially under non-natural conditions.²¹⁻²⁵ Cell-free systems
29 have enabled the biosynthesis of *R* and *S* enantiomers of 3-HBA and derivatives
30 like poly(hydroxybutyrate) from various substrates.^{22, 26-28} Among these, glucose,
31 small organic acids, and vinyl esters are the most commonly used feedstocks
32 (**Figure 1C**). From glucose, 3-HBA is produced by linking glycolysis and pyruvate
33 decarboxylation to a truncated reverse β -oxidation pathway (rBOX). This route
34 involves a non-decarboxylating Claisen condensation of acetyl-CoA catalyzed by
35 thiolases,²⁹ followed by asymmetric reduction of a ketoacyl-CoA intermediate
36 catalyzed by an NAD(P)H reductase. The last step is the hydrolysis of the 3-
37 hydroxyacyl-CoA, releasing 3-HBA and coenzyme A (CoA), catalyzed by a
38 thioesterase. In contrast, organic acids are first activated to acyl-CoAs by ATP-
39 dependent acyl-CoA synthetases. These are then funneled into the same
40 truncated rBOX. Vinyl esters follow a different path, though. They undergo abiotic
41 thiolysis in the presence of CoA, yielding acetyl-CoA to prime the truncated rBOX.
42 Acetaldehyde is released in this reaction and acts as an electron donor to recycle
43 the reduced nicotinamide cofactors needed by the reductase. Hence, vinyl esters

1 act as both acyl and electron donors for the biosynthesis of 3-hydroxy acids
2 through an ATP-independent pathway.

3 Despite progress, using short aliphatic alcohols like ethanol to synthesize 3-
4 HBA through an in vitro anabolic pathway remains a challenge.^{21, 30-34} One major
5 limitation is the higher energy barrier of oxidative acylation required to form acyl-
6 CoAs from these alcohols. This step is key to starting the biosynthetic cascade.
7 The second limitation is the redox imbalance, as the oxidative acylation of
8 alcohols generates excess reducing power, which is not fully consumed during
9 ketoacyl-CoA reduction. This accumulation of reducing power limits the
10 progression of the cascade, thereby hindering the activation of aldehydes by CoA
11 and leading to a premature halt of the reaction. Cell-free extracts overcome this
12 issue using endogenous enzymes by either dissipating the redox excess into the
13 metabolic background,³⁵ or incorporating engineered redox valves that rewire it
14 into the main reaction.^{28, 36} However, maintaining redox balance with isolated
15 enzymes remains a difficult task and requires precise regulation. Despite these
16 complications, bio-based alcohols like ethanol are attractive feedstocks to
17 synthesize 3-hydroxyacids.^{34, 35, 37, 38}

18 Beyond issues related to metabolic balance, other obstacles limit cell-free
19 biosynthetic pathways: poor protein stability, enzyme compartmentalization,
20 cofactor supply, and cross-inhibition issues, among others.^{20,39} Enzyme
21 immobilization onto porous carriers emerges as a solution for both problems
22 when designing a wise immobilization strategy. There are many examples where
23 immobilization enhances enzyme stability and allows biocatalyst integration into
24 flow systems.⁴⁰⁻⁴³ Besides, the spatial organization of multi-enzymatic systems
25 within porous carriers can also improve intermediate transfer between active
26 sites.⁴⁴⁻⁵⁰ This strategic arrangement can create favorable intraparticle gradients
27 of intermediates and cofactors, enhancing overall reaction kinetics. Furthermore,
28 proximity channeling effects and macromolecular crowding also contribute to
29 enhancing the performance of the immobilized multi-enzyme systems.⁴⁹⁻⁵⁴

30 In this work, we propose the biosynthesis of 3-hydroxy acids from primary
31 alcohols through multi-functional heterogeneous biocatalysts that can be
32 implemented in a packed-bed reactor for continuous operation (**Figure 1D and**
33 **Figure S1**). The process involves an oxidative condensation cascade catalyzed
34 by a cell-free enzyme system immobilized on agarose beads. The cascade
35 begins with two consecutive NAD-dependent oxidations that convert the primary
36 alcohol to its coenzyme A thioester. This acyl-CoA then enters a truncated rBOX
37 pathway to produce the enantiomerically pure (*S*)-hydroxy acid. The process
38 uses two cofactors, CoA and NADH, which are regenerated during the reaction.
39 However, the stoichiometry creates a redox imbalance in NAD(H), solved by
40 introducing a redox valve based on a promiscuous dehydrogenase and using
41 acetone as a co-substrate. The spatial configuration of co-immobilized enzymes
42 was key to maintaining an internal redox balance that steers both the oxidative

1 thioesterification and the asymmetric reduction, driving the overall reaction
 2 cascade forward. Herein, we demonstrate that bio-based primary alcohols can
 3 be valorized to chiral polyfunctional molecules mediated by an acyl-CoA pathway
 4 that opens new avenues for sustainable biosynthesis. This approach offers a
 5 promising strategy in synthetic biology for building complex chemicals from
 6 renewable resources with high precision. To the best of our knowledge, no
 7 chemical process can achieve this stepwise transformation with the same
 8 precision and simultaneity as this enzymatic system.

9

10 **Figure 1:** Biotransformation of carbon sources in 3-hydroxyacids. A) Chemical or fermentative
 11 depolymerization of poly(hydroxyalkanoates). B) Fermentative approaches using native or engineered
 12 microbial cells to transform carbon sources into the target product. C) Cell-free enzyme systems to convert
 13 sugars (through endogenous glycolysis/oxidative decarboxylation) and vinyl esters (through abiotic thiolysis)
 14 into the target product in batch reactors. D) Artificial immobilized multi-enzyme systems to continuously
 15 transform primary alcohols into 3-hydroxy acids operated in a packed-bed reactor (this work).

1 Results

2 Kinetics and substrate scope of an engineered CoA-acylating 3 dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica* (Δ NPduP)

4 The 1,2-propanediol utilization in *Salmonella enterica* relies on the *pdu*
5 operon. This operon clusters genes encoding enzymes that convert the diol into
6 propionic acid, along with genes for structural proteins that assemble into
7 bacterial microcompartments (BMCs) to isolate the pathway from central
8 metabolism.⁵⁵ One of the enzymes involved in this catabolic pathway is a CoA-
9 acylating propionaldehyde dehydrogenase (SePduP) encoded by the *pduP* gene.
10 This enzyme catalyzes the oxidation of propionaldehyde to propionyl-CoA using
11 NAD⁺ as an electron acceptor and CoA as an acyl acceptor (**Figure 2A**).

12 **Figure 2** A) Scheme of oxidative thioesterification of aldehydes catalyzed by Δ NPduP. B) Relative activity
13 of Δ NPduP toward different aldehydes (see Table S3) at 30 °C and pH 8. The activity toward propionaldehyde
14 (2b) was taken as reference (130 U mg⁻¹). C) Scheme of all aldehydes used in this work. D) Kinetic
15 parameters of Δ NPduP toward different substrates and cofactors. ^aKinetic parameters taken from Lan et
16 al.⁵⁶ Data in panel B show the mean of two independent experiments, where the error bars represent their
17 standard deviation.

18 However, this enzyme has never been characterized in vitro for its oxidative
19 (CoA-acylating) reaction. In this work, we envisioned the potential of this enzyme
20 for the ATP-free synthesis of acyl-CoAs through acylating CoA with aldehydes.

1 To assess the capacity of SePduP for oxidizing different aldehydes to acyl-CoAs,
2 we optimized the *pduP* gene and expressed it in *E. coli* BL21 (DE3).
3 Nevertheless, the wild-type protein was highly insoluble and presented a high
4 tendency to precipitate when purified. Inspired by previous works, we
5 hypothesized that the protein precipitation was driven by the presence of an N-
6 terminal binding domain to assemble SePduP into BMCs.⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰ To confirm our
7 hypothesis and increase protein solubility, we prepared an N-terminal truncated
8 version of SePduP, named as Δ NPduP, where the first 28 amino acids of the N-
9 terminal were deleted in the encoding gene (**Table S1-S2**). This gene deletion
10 resulted in a well-expressed protein (Δ NPduP) with a solubility 10-fold higher than
11 the wild-type variant (**Figure S2**).

12 With a soluble enzyme in hand, we assessed the substrate scope of Δ NPduP
13 by testing its oxidative activity on a range of aldehydes (**Table S3**) to synthesize
14 a variety of acyl-CoAs (**Figure 2A**). This engineered enzyme exhibited a broad
15 aldehyde scope, showing a specific activity of 130 U mg⁻¹ for propionaldehyde
16 (**2b**) (**Figure 2B**). Using this activity as a reference, Δ NPduP demonstrated
17 moderate-to-high relative activity (>40%) toward short aliphatic aldehydes (**2a**-
18 70 U mg⁻¹, **2c**- 112 U mg⁻¹, **2i**- 98.5 U mg⁻¹, or **2j**- 85 U mg⁻¹), but low relative
19 activity (<20%) toward bulkier aliphatic aldehydes (**2e**- 30.7 U mg⁻¹, **2k**- 20.1 U
20 mg⁻¹, **2l**- 8.9 U mg⁻¹, **2m**- 9.9 U mg⁻¹) and aromatic aldehydes (**2f**- 18.5 U mg⁻¹
21 and **2g**- 0 U mg⁻¹) (**Figure 2B-C**). Following the same trend as the specific activity,
22 the catalytic efficiency ($k_{cat} K_m^{-1}$) toward **2b** (2,050 mM⁻¹s⁻¹) was 108 times higher
23 than toward **2a** (19 mM⁻¹s⁻¹) because of the increased K_m toward the shorter
24 aldehyde (**Figures 2C** and **S2**). Surprisingly, the catalytic efficiency of Δ NPduP
25 for **2b** was 3.7- and 7-fold lower than its efficiency toward **2c** (13,883 mM⁻¹s⁻¹)
26 and **2d** (7,497 mM⁻¹s⁻¹), respectively, despite exhibiting lower specific activity
27 toward these larger aldehydes under assay conditions. This discrepancy is
28 attributed to the higher affinity of Δ NPduP for larger linear aldehydes. The K_m
29 values were 1 order of magnitude lower toward **2c** and **2d** than toward **2b** (**Figure**
30 **2D** and **S3**). Finally, we confirmed that Δ NPduP prefers NAD⁺ to NADP⁺ by a
31 factor of 10, similarly to other CoA-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenases from
32 other organisms.⁶¹⁻⁶³ When comparing the kinetic parameters of the CoA-
33 acylating reaction with those of the CoA-deacylating reactions, we observed that
34 the enzyme generally exhibits a higher K_m for short aldehydes (**2a**) than for short
35 acyl-CoAs (e.g., acetyl-CoA), yet the k_{cat} for acetaldehyde is an order of
36 magnitude higher than for acetyl-CoA (**Figure 2D**).⁵⁶ Although the catalytic
37 efficiency toward acetaldehyde is lower than that for acetyl-CoA, the CoA-
38 acylating rate will dominate the reaction when the aldehyde is in high excess
39 relative to CoA. In addition to kinetic parameters, we also determined that
40 Δ NPduP presents an optimum pH of 8, retaining over 70% of its enzymatic activity
41 at pH 7 and 9. However, the activity of Δ NPduP decreased below 40% at more
42 extreme pH values (6 and 10) (**Figure S4**). Regarding the thermal stability,

1 Δ NPduP presents some hints of thermostability as it retained 50% of its initial
2 activity after 2.5 h incubation at 65 °C and pH 7 (**Figure S5**).

3 Once Δ NPduP was biochemically characterized, we evaluated its ability to
4 quantitatively synthesize acyl-CoAs from aldehydes. Because Δ NPduP exhibited
5 the highest enzymatic activity toward propionaldehyde (**2b**), we selected this
6 aldehyde as a model substrate. The enzyme was incubated with **2b** and free CoA
7 as a cofactor, along with either excess or substoichiometric amounts of NAD⁺,
8 and supplemented with either dithiothreitol (DTT) or tris(2-
9 carboxyethyl)phosphine (TCEP). These reductants were necessary to maintain
10 the redox state of Δ NPduP.^{61, 64} We achieved 97% analytical yield (A. Yield) of
11 propionyl-CoA using TCEP compared to the 73% obtained with DTT (**Figure**
12 **S6A**). We propose that the greater stability of TCEP helps maintain Δ NPduP in a
13 more catalytically competent redox state than when using DTT.⁶⁵ Using
14 substoichiometric amounts of NAD⁺, we coupled Δ NPduP with a water-forming
15 NADH oxidase from *Lactobacillus pentosus* (LpNOX) as a cofactor regeneration
16 system. We just achieved 20% A. yield and a significant decrease in the pool of
17 free CoA (**Figure S6A**). As the decrease of CoA concentration was also observed
18 in the reaction controls without the enzymes, we discarded the CoA degradation
19 driven by LpNOX. When inspecting the UPLC/MS chromatograms of the reaction
20 controls (without enzymes), we identified CoAS-SCoA dimers in those reactions
21 with exogenous FAD⁺ (**Figure S6B-D**).

22 **Design and optimization of a heterogeneous biocatalyst to transform** 23 **primary alcohols into thioesters.**

24 Once we confirmed the potential of Δ NPduP to synthesize acyl-CoAs from
25 aldehydes, we attempted to in situ produce these aldehydes by coupling an
26 alcohol dehydrogenase able to oxidize primary alcohols. These in situ-produced
27 aldehydes would be converted into acyl-CoAs by Δ NPduP. This approach allowed
28 us to avoid problems caused by high aldehyde concentrations in the reaction,
29 such as enzyme inactivation through chemical modification, aldehyde
30 evaporation, and nonspecific side reactions.⁶⁶⁻⁶⁸ In theory, this bi-enzymatic
31 system promotes the sequential double oxidation and thioesterification of primary
32 alcohols to form the corresponding acyl-CoAs.

33 When we determined the ΔG of the overall reaction cascade, the oxidative
34 acylation of alcohols was slightly endergonic, $\Delta G = 2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Thus, the NAD-
35 dependent oxidative thioesterification of ethanol is 3-fold less favorable
36 thermodynamically than the exergonic ATP-dependent phosphorylative
37 thioesterification of acetate ($\Delta G = -3.53 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) (**Figure 3A**). This ΔG value is
38 even smaller than that estimated for the cellular phosphorylative thioesterification
39 coupled to the pyrophosphate hydrolysis ($\Delta G = -7.38 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). Hence, the
40 thermodynamics of the oxidative thioesterification highlight the importance of
41 coupling this bi-enzymatic system with a very efficient regeneration of the NAD⁺
42 to shift the equilibrium toward the CoA-acylating reaction.

1 **Figure 3:** A) Standard Gibbs free energy changes of each reaction step using eQuilibrator⁶⁹ at pH 8, pMg2,
2 and ionic strength of 0.2 M. Formation of acetyl-CoA through oxidative thioesterification of ethanol is shown
3 in orange, and the ATP-dependent S-acylation of CoA is indicated in yellow (in the absence of
4 pyrophosphatase). Numbers refer to the substrate (**1**: alcohol for BsADH or acetate for ACS), intermediate
5 (**2**: aldehyde), and product (**3**: acyl-CoA). B) Scheme of oxidative thioesterification of alcohols catalyzed by
6 HB-1 series. The * indicates the regeneration of the second NADH produced by ΔNPduP, using the acetone-
7 based recycling system. C) Oxidative thioesterification of 10 mM ethanol by three different Heterogeneous
8 Biocatalysts (HB-1.1, HB-1.2, and HB-1.3) with different BsADH:ΔNPduP ratios using 50 mM acetone as co-
9 substrate. D) Oxidative thioesterification of 10 mM of 1-propanol by three different Heterogeneous
10 Biocatalysts (HB-1.1, HB-1.2, and HB-1.3) with different BsADH:ΔNPduP ratios using 50 mM acetone as co-
11 substrate. Data in panels C and D show the mean of two independent experiments, where the error bars
12 represent their standard deviation.

13 In this context, we selected the alcohol dehydrogenase from *Bacillus*
14 *stearothermophilus* (BsADH) as a candidate because its broad substrate scope
15 allowed the oxidation of primary alcohols.^{32, 33, 70} As a recycling system, we
16 discarded the conventional use of FAD-dependent NOX enzymes because of the
17 dimerization of the free CoA. Alternatively, we proposed the reduction of acetone
18 to isopropanol catalyzed by BsADH (**Table S4**),⁷¹ as an oxygen-independent
19 NAD⁺ recycling system. Although in our experience, cell-free enzyme systems in
20 solution usually reach higher yields, their application is limited to one reaction
21 cycle, as free enzymes are difficult to reuse for consecutive batch cycles. To
22 increase their operational stability and reusability, we immobilized these two
23 enzymes on porous carriers based on crosslinked agarose microbeads (AG). To
24 find the optimal immobilization protocols for the co-immobilization of these two
25 enzymes, we evaluated four immobilization chemistries. The agarose-based
26 carriers were functionalized with: 1) glyoxyl groups (AG-G) for irreversible

1 covalent binding via the ϵ -amino groups of exposed lysine residues, 2) Co^{2+} -
2 chelates (AG- Co^{2+}) for affinity immobilization through the His-tag of enzymes, and
3 either polyallylamine (AG-PAH) or polyethyleneimine (AG-PEI) for ionic
4 interactions with the exposed acidic residues of enzyme surfaces. Also, we tested
5 a triheterofunctional carrier where the agarose beads were activated with 4)
6 aldehydes, cobalt-chelates, and positively charged amine groups (AG- Co^{2+} /G/A).
7 This latter carrier has recently been applied to co-immobilize several multi-
8 enzyme systems.^{40, 72}

9 The highest activity and thermal stability for the studied enzymes were
10 achieved under specific immobilization conditions (**Table S5 and Figure S7**).
11 ΔNPduP immobilized on AG-G resulted in an 18% immobilization efficiency and
12 retained 95% of its initial activity after 7.5 hours at 65 °C (**Figure S7A**). BsADH
13 was immobilized on either AG-G and AG-PEI, showing immobilization efficiencies
14 of 37 and 99%, respectively, improving the results previously reported for AG-
15 Co^{2+} and AG- Co^{2+} /G/A.⁷² However, these new immobilization chemistries
16 reduced the enzyme thermal stability when compared to the soluble enzyme
17 (**Figure S7B**). According to these results, we selected AG-G as the consensus
18 carrier to co-immobilize the two enzymes. We prepared three new heterogeneous
19 biocatalysts, with different BsADH: ΔNPduP activity ratios; 5:1, 1:1, and 1:5,
20 named as HB-1.1, HB-1.2 or HB-1.3, respectively (**Table S5**). The heterogeneous
21 biocatalyst with the highest ratio BsADH: ΔNPduP (HB-1.1) rendered the highest
22 acyl-CoA A. yields (**Figure 3C-D**). This result demonstrates that the oxygen-
23 independent acetone/BsADH pair is an efficient system for NAD^+ recycling in this
24 cascade. As expected, the biocatalysts of the HB-1 series were more efficient in
25 synthesizing propionyl-CoA than acetyl-CoA, given the 6-fold higher catalytic
26 efficiency of ΔNPduP toward **2c** regarding **2b** (**Figure 2D**). In this acetone-driven
27 NAD^+ recycling system, BsADH functions as a redox valve. It oxidizes primary
28 alcohols to their corresponding aldehydes when NAD^+ is abundant, but reduces
29 acetone to isopropanol when NADH accumulates. This is possible because
30 BsADH presents a 30-fold higher K_m toward isopropanol than toward ethanol
31 (**Table S4**), preventing competition for NAD^+ between the oxidation of isopropanol
32 and ethanol. The concept of the redox valve has been previously utilized in others
33 cell-free biosynthetic pathways to surpass the basic cofactor imbalance issue.³⁶

34 **Design and optimization of the heterogeneous biocatalysts to transform** 35 **ethanol into 3-hydroxy butyric acid.**

36 After developing the HB-1 series for the ATP-independent transformation of
37 primary alcohols into acyl-CoAs, we coupled them with a well-established
38 enzymatic system that sequentially converts acyl-CoAs into 3-hydroxy acids.
39 Herein, the oxidative thioesterification of primary alcohols was coupled to a
40 truncated rBOX pathway. As a model reaction, ethanol was sequentially oxidized
41 to acetyl-CoA by BsADH and ΔNPduP , followed by a non-decarboxylative Claisen
42 condensation of the 2 acetyl-CoAs catalyzed by a thiolase 5 from *Ascaris suum*

1 (AsTHL5). The resulting acetoacetyl-CoA is then asymmetrically reduced by an
2 S-selective 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase from *Thermus thermophilus*
3 HB27 (TtHBDH) to yield 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA that is finally hydrolyzed by a
4 thioesterase from *Escherichia coli* (EcTesB) to yield (S)-3-hydroxybutyric acid (3-
5 HBA) (**Figure 4**). Without redox cofactor recycling, the cascade presents a $\Delta G =$
6 $-5.02 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ calculated by eQuilibrator,⁶⁹ about four times higher than when
7 the reaction is initiated from (ATP-independent) or acetate (ATP-dependent).
8 Moreover, if no NAD^+ recycling system is coupled, this cascade is redox
9 unbalanced due to the accumulation of 3 molecules of NADH per molecule of 3-
10 HBA. The thermodynamic analysis underscores the inherent difficulty of
11 synthesizing 3-hydroxy acids from primary alcohols.

12 We faced the redox imbalance challenge by investigating the compatibility of
13 the acetone-driven recycling system with the asymmetric reduction of the
14 condensed ketoacyl-CoA intermediate. First, we intended the oxidative
15 condensation of ethanol (**1a**) into 3-HBA using soluble enzymes and sub-
16 stoichiometric amounts of redox (NAD^+) and acylating (CoA) cofactors. Working
17 with soluble enzymes, we observed no production of 3-HBA, yet acetate was
18 accumulated (**Figure S8**), indicating the undesired hydrolysis of acetyl-CoA (**3a**).
19 We suggest that oxidative acylation produces and accumulates acetyl-CoA,
20 which is not further converted into 3-HBA. In our hypothesis, the BsADH-driven
21 reduction of acetone likely competes with TtHBDH for NADH, decoupling the
22 oxidative activation module and the condensation/reduction/hydrolysis module.
23 Consequently, EcTesB hydrolyzes the accumulated acetyl-CoA to acetate, a
24 dead-end product that derails ethanol from 3-HBA formation (**Figure 4**). To rescue
25 TtHBDH from this competition, we added glucose and a thermostable variant of
26 the glucose dehydrogenase from *Bacillus subtilis* (BsGDH) to the system,⁷³ yet
27 the system failed to produce the 3-HBA and acetate (**Figure S8**). This points out
28 a competition between BsGDH and the pair BsADH/ ΔNPduP for the NAD^+ ,
29 preventing the formation of acetyl-CoA and consequently of its hydrolysis
30 product, acetate.

1 **Figure 4.** Scheme of the model reaction to transform ethanol into 3-hydroxybutyric acid (3-HBA)
 2 through a 5-enzyme, 6-reaction step system catalyzed by the alcohol dehydrogenase from *Bacillus*
 3 *stearothermophilus* (BsADH; **R1**, oxidation of ethanol, and **R6**, reduction of acetone), the engineered CoA-
 4 acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica* (Δ NPduP; **R2**, oxidative thioesterification), the
 5 thiolase from *Ralstonia eutropha* (ReTHL; **R3**, non-decarboxylative Claisen condensation), the 3-
 6 hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase from *Thermus thermophilus* (TtHBDH; **R4**, asymmetric reduction), and
 7 the thioesterase B from *Escherichia coli* (EcTesB; **R5**, hydrolysis). The undesired hydrolysis of acetyl-CoA
 8 catalyzed by EcTesB is represented with a red dashed arrow.

9 As compartmentalization was proven successful for a bienzymatic system
 10 composed of TtHBDH and NOX in a previous study,⁴⁹ we decided to perform this
 11 biosynthetic pathway using heterogeneous biocatalysts. To do so, we combined
 12 the series of HB-1 composed of co-immobilized BsADH and Δ NPduP with
 13 AsTHL5, TtHBDH, and EcTesB co-immobilized on AG-Co²⁺ (HB-2). Using this
 14 combination, we detected 3-HBA (0.240 ± 0.001 mM) and acetate (3.8 ± 0.1 mM)
 15 at very low titer though (**Figure S9**). The compartmentalization of the oxidative
 16 activation module and the condensation/reduction/hydrolysis module succeeded
 17 in yielding (S)-3-HBA according to the exquisite selectivity of TtHBDH previously
 18 reported.²² As both 3-HBA and acetate were detected using 1 mM of NAD⁺, the
 19 NAD⁺ was recycled at least 7 times according to the pathway stoichiometry (3
 20 and 2 moles of NAD⁺ per mol of 3-HBA and acetate, respectively). This was an
 21 encouraging starting point to optimize the multi-functional heterogeneous
 22 biocatalyst.

23 When we increased the ethanol concentration from 50 to 200 mM, we
 24 achieved a 10-fold increase in 3-HBA titer using the same spatial configuration.
 25 By testing the HB-1 series in combination with HB-2, we unexpectedly found that
 26 HB-1.3 with the less optimal BsADH: Δ NPduP activity ratio for acyl-CoA

1 biosynthesis was the most efficient heterogeneous biocatalyst for the 3-HBA
2 production, achieving a maximum titer of 4.0 ± 0.2 mM 3-HBA and 15.30 ± 0.06
3 mM acetate (**Figure 5A**). HB-1.1, which achieved the higher acyl-CoA yield,
4 produced 2.16 ± 0.02 mM 3-HBA, 2-fold less 3-HBA titer than HB-1.3. One
5 limitation of this system is the reversibility of the interactions established between
6 the His-tagged enzymes and the carrier in HB-2, which might limit the overall
7 operational stability of the system due to enzyme leaching issues. To maximize
8 the operational stability of this multi-functional heterogeneous biocatalyst, we
9 intended the co-immobilization of the 5 enzymes first on AG-Co²⁺ through their
10 His-tags (HB-3), and then on AG-G. Unfortunately, HB-3 failed to produce 3-HBA
11 but accumulated acetate, suggesting impaired activity of either AsTHL5 or
12 TtHBDH, disrupting the progression of the cascade. Likewise, AsTHL5 was fully
13 inactivated when immobilized on AG-G, precluding the fabrication of this
14 heterogeneous biocatalyst. As an alternative, we decided to replace AsTHL5 with
15 a thiolase from *Ralstonia eutropha* (ReTHL) since this enzyme was reported to
16 be efficiently immobilized on AG-G.⁷⁴ Hence, we co-immobilized ReTHL,
17 TtHBDH, and EcTesB on AG-G, resulting in HB-4, which was mixed with HB-1.3,
18 where BsADH and Δ NPduP were also co-immobilized through the aldehyde
19 chemistry. This combination of heterogeneous biocatalysts increased the 3-HBA
20 titer up to 6.52 ± 0.08 , a 63% higher 3-HBA titer compared to that achieved by
21 HB-1.3 and HB-2 (containing AsTHL5 on AG-Co²⁺) (4.0 ± 0.2 mM) (**Figure 5A-**
22 **B**). Thus, the combination of a new thiolase with a more stabilizing immobilization
23 chemistry improved the throughput of the immobilized biosynthetic cascade.⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷
24 Herein, the five enzymes were immobilized using the same chemistry but were
25 physically segregated, having the oxidative acylation module in one particle and
26 the condensation/reduction/hydrolysis module in another. To improve their spatial
27 localization, we co-immobilized all five enzymes on AG-G, fabricating a new
28 biocatalyst named HB-5.1. This multi-functional heterogeneous biocatalyst
29 produced 7.86 ± 0.029 mM 3-HB (**Figure 5B**), increasing the target titer by 20%
30 compared to the system immobilized separately (HB-1.3 + HB-4).

Figure 5. Effect of enzyme spatial distribution on the performance of multi-functional heterogeneous biocatalysts. A) 3-HBA (purple) and acetate (grey) titers from different combinations of heterogeneous biocatalysts (HB) using AsTHL5 as thiolase. 25 mg of each HB was resuspended in the reaction mixture with a ratio of 1/5 (w/v). B) 3-HBA (purple) and acetate (grey) titers from different combinations of heterogeneous biocatalysts using ReTHL as thiolase. 25 mg of each HB was resuspended in the reaction mixture with a ratio of 1/5 (w/v). C, D) Single-particle analysis of the heterogeneous biocatalysts after 22 hours of reaction. The system includes either HB-1.3 labeled with Rhodamine B isocyanate (RhB, shown in red) combined with HB-4 (C), or HB-5.1. The left images show the autofluorescence of NADH in blue, while the right images show either the overlay of the brightfield and the Rhodamine B attached to HB-1.3 in red (C) or just the brightfield (D). E) 3-HBA (purple) and acetate (grey) titers, as well as the acetate/3-HBA ratio

1 (black dots) obtained with either the immobilized system (HB5 series with different enzyme loadings (see
2 Table S6)) or the soluble ones operated with different CoA and acetone concentrations. 40 mg of each HB
3 was mixed with the reaction mix in a ratio of 1/5 (w/v). The soluble reactions were carried out as described
4 in the Methods section. F) Bulk (outside particle) and intraparticle (inside particle) NAD⁺, NADH, CoA, and
5 acetyl-CoA concentrations of the reaction catalyzed by HB-5.2, and the cofactor concentration in the reaction
6 bulk catalyzed by the homogeneous reaction with pure enzymes (homogeneous reaction). Cofactor
7 concentration was determined by UPLC/MS as indicated in the Methods section. G) Merged Confocal Laser
8 Scanning Microscopy (CLSM) 40X images of HB-8.2 formed by one unlabeled enzyme (ReTHL) and the left
9 4 enzymes labeled with compatible fluorophores; BsADH (RhB, λ_{ex} : 561 nm, orange color); Δ NPduP (Atto
10 390, λ_{ex} : 405 nm, blue color), EcTesB (FTIC; λ_{ex} : 488 nm), and TtHBDH (A647, λ_{ex} : 633 nm, red color)
11 obtained from HB-5.2. The scheme on the right represents the proposed extraparticle and intraparticle
12 diffusion paths for all intermediates involved in the biosynthetic cascade.

13 To better understand how spatial organization affects pathway performance,
14 we quantified all intermediates via UPLC/MS after 16 hours at 30°C. For CoA
15 intermediates, only free CoA and acetyl-CoA were detected. The CoA/acetyl-CoA
16 ratio was close to 1 in reactions yielding the highest 3-HBA titers (**Figure S10**).
17 UPLC analysis also revealed the presence of both NAD redox species at the end
18 of the reaction, with a molar excess of NAD⁺ over NADH ranging from 30 to 5.
19 Higher titers correlated with a 20-fold molar excess of NAD⁺ over NADH (**Figure**
20 **S10**). Redox balance reached a pseudo-steady state, with NADH levels
21 stabilizing at 40 μ M, driving the asymmetric reduction of the 3-ketoacyl-CoA
22 intermediate. This trend was observed in both co-immobilized (HB-5.1) and
23 physically segregated systems (HB-1.3 + HB-4). Next, we exploited time-lapse
24 epifluorescence microscopy to track the intraparticle NADH density, leveraging
25 its autofluorescence under blue light (**Figure 5C-D and S11**). In both reactions,
26 an equilibrium was achieved after 5 hours of reaction, similarly to the results
27 obtained with the UPLC/MS analysis (**Figures S10C-D**). This equilibrium was
28 maintained for 24 hours. Interestingly, HB-5.1 presented only one population of
29 particles with similar intraparticle fluorescence density. In contrast, the
30 segregated system (HB-1.3 + HB-4) exhibited two particle populations with
31 different intraparticle fluorescence intensity. The particles with the lowest blue
32 fluorescence (NADH) correspond to those particles labeled with rhodamine (red),
33 corresponding to HB-1.3. As single-particle fluorescence informs about
34 intraparticle NADH concentration, we suggest that in the physically segregated
35 system, NADH is produced in HB-1.3, diffuses into the bulk, and then enters HB-
36 4, where it is accumulated and consumed. In contrast, in HB-5.1, NADH is both
37 produced and consumed within the same bead (**Figure 5C-D**). The differences
38 found in the intraparticle NADH concentration explain the variation in 3-HBA titers
39 depending on the spatial configuration of the heterogeneous biocatalytic
40 systems. Hence, this single-particle study confirms bulk results, demonstrating
41 that the intraparticle NAD(H) redox ratio plays a crucial role in maximizing 3-HBA
42 titer.

43 Once the best spatial configuration for the immobilized enzymatic cascade
44 was selected, we conducted an *in silico* optimization using COPASI software as
45 previously done for other multi-enzyme systems in solution.^{78, 79} Since the

1 software is not designed to model mass transfer in immobilized systems, we
2 simulated the soluble enzyme cascade using the kinetic and thermodynamic
3 parameters of the free enzymes (**Table S4**). Hence, we created semi-quantitative
4 models (**Table S7-S8**) to find bottlenecks and predict qualitative information about
5 reaction bottlenecks and optimum enzyme concentrations. We tuned the model
6 to achieve a similar 3-HBA titer under the same reaction conditions and enzyme
7 concentrations used in HB-5.1. We found that Δ NPduP was the rate-limiting
8 enzyme, and that EcTesB acted as a kinetic trap due to its undesired hydrolytic
9 activity toward acetyl-CoA (**3a**). After parameter scanning of all enzymes
10 (**Figures S12-S13**). The simulations suggested increasing the Δ NPduP loading
11 and reducing the EcTesB one, keeping an excess of Δ NPduP regarding BsADH.
12 Finally, COPASI models also suggested increasing the acetone concentration up
13 to 300 mM to maximize the 3-HBA titer. Following the COPASI model predictions,
14 we fabricated a new version of this heterogeneous biocatalyst named HB-5.2.
15 The five enzymes were also co-immobilized on AG-G; however, this version
16 contains a higher loading of Δ NPduP and a lower loading of EcTesB compared
17 to HB-5.1.

18 When HB-5.2 was tested in the presence of 300 mM of acetone as suggested
19 by the COPASI model, we detected 15.7 ± 0.31 mM 3-HBA, a titer two times higher
20 than that achieved with HB-5.1 using 100 mM acetone (**Figure 5E**). Next, we
21 intended to increase the total turnover number of CoA by decreasing the CoA
22 concentration in the reaction to 0.5 mM. Surprisingly, less CoA led to an increased
23 titer of 18 ± 0.18 mM 3-HBA, resulting in a TTN_{CoA} of 72. This higher titer reflects
24 improved performance of Δ NPduP, which is inhibited by free CoA (**Figure 2D**,
25 $K_i^{CoA} = 1.3$ mM). Despite the thermodynamically unfavorable non-decarboxylative
26 Claisen condensation, the system efficiently accumulates acetyl-CoA and
27 removes free CoA and 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA. This enables ReTHL (a
28 biosynthetic thiolase) to drive the reaction forward, preventing it from working in
29 the reverse direction.^{29, 80, 81} HB-5.2 also increased the acetate production up to
30 33 ± 0.03 mM, yet the acetate:3-HBA molar ratio was reduced to 1.86 compared
31 to the 2.2 ratio found with HB-5.1 using 100 mM acetone and 1 mM CoA (**Figure**
32 **5E**). The reduction of this ratio points out the mitigation of ethanol derailment from
33 the main pathway when the heterogeneous biocatalyst and the reaction media
34 were optimized. Under these optimal conditions, we decided to perform the
35 biosynthetic pathway with the free enzymes. We only detected 2.54 ± 0.037 mM
36 3-HBA with an accumulation of 21.2 ± 0.47 mM of acetate, which means an
37 acetate:3-HBA ratio of 8.5 (**Figure 5E**). When we analyzed the accumulation of
38 cofactors both in the bulk and inside the biocatalyst particles at the end of the
39 reaction course, we found intriguing differences (**Figure 5F**). On the one hand,
40 the acetyl-CoA in the bulk was 9 times higher than the CoA concentration,
41 regardless the system was free or immobilized. However, the similar
42 concentrations of these two CoA species inside the beads indicate a gradient of
43 CoA intermediates between the bulk and the particles. On the other hand, the

1 molar excess of NAD⁺ over NADH was 99 times in the bulk of the reaction
2 catalyzed by the free enzymes. In comparison, on those reactions catalyzed by
3 HB-5.2, the molar excess of NAD⁺ over NADH was lower, being only 24 times.
4 Even more interesting was the fact that the molar excess of NAD⁺ to NADH
5 decayed to 2.3 times inside the biocatalyst's particle. This means that co-
6 immobilized enzymes are exposed to a higher NADH concentration than free
7 ones, which can enhance the asymmetric reduction of the acetoacetyl-CoA
8 intermediate. Thus, differences in cofactor concentrations between the bulk
9 phase and the interior of the heterogeneous biocatalyst give rise to intermediate
10 gradients that cannot form in the corresponding soluble system. These gradients
11 may explain why the immobilized system outperforms the soluble one. To gain
12 deeper insight into the formation of these gradients at the microscopic level, we
13 analyzed the spatial organization of the five enzymes across the surface of the
14 porous carrier forming HB-5.2. Using confocal laser scanning microscopy
15 (CLSM), we performed co-localization studies with enzyme samples spiked with
16 fluorophore-labeled enzymes (**Figure 5G and S14**). According to the infiltration
17 profile and the Pearson coefficient, BsADH and Δ NPduP co-localized at the outer
18 surface of the biocatalysts (**Figure S15**). Contrarily, ReTHL, TtHBDH, and
19 EcTesB were infiltrated to a higher extent inside the HB-5.2 particle, resulting in
20 a lower degree of co-localization between them. Based on the intraparticle
21 enzyme segregation and cofactors gradients described above, we propose a
22 diffusion path where the NAD⁺ and CoA from the bulk first find the oxidative
23 activation module, accumulating acetyl-CoA and NADH inside the beads, where
24 the downstream enzymes are localized (**Figure 5G**). This spatial organization
25 enhances the throughput of the cascade through a suitable diffusion gradient of
26 intermediates, otherwise impossible using free enzymes. This result is supported
27 by our initial attempts under non-optimized conditions, where free enzymes
28 produced no 3-HBA from ethanol. Therefore, the co-immobilization of this 5-
29 enzyme system provides a suitable confined environment to create gradients of
30 intermediates, pushing the pathway toward the final product, and minimizing
31 intermediate derailments. Hence, the cofactor imbalance within the enzymatic
32 system is resolved through the strategic spatial arrangement of confined
33 enzymes. This setup mimics the spatial organization of biosynthetic pathways in
34 the cell milieu, enabling out-of-equilibrium reaction cascades and overcoming
35 thermodynamic barriers.

36 **Scope of HB-5.2 toward esters, aldehydes, and primary alcohols**

37 After the optimization of a heterogeneous biocatalyst (HB-5.2) to maximize
38 the titer of 3-HBA from ethanol, we assessed its scope to transform other starting
39 materials to ultimately produce 3-HBA. Using 50 mM of either precursors (esters)
40 or derivatives (aldehydes) of ethanol and HB-5.2 at 20% (w:v) catalyst load, we
41 determined the 3-HBA titers (**Figure 6A**). Starting from acetaldehyde and vinyl
42 acetate (an ester that, upon abiotic thiolysis with CoA, produces acetyl-CoA and

1 acetaldehyde), the titers were limited to 0.19 or 1.6 mM 3-HBA, respectively. On
2 the contrary, when pure ethyl acetate is used as substrate in the presence of an
3 immobilized lipase (Novozyme 435) together with HB-5.2, both acetate and
4 ethanol are released, and the ethanol is sequentially converted into up to
5 6.6 ± 0.03 mM of 3-HBA. The titer from the ethyl ester was slightly higher than
6 starting from ethanol under the same reaction conditions and biocatalyst loads.
7 Using ethyl acetate as a starting material captured our interest as this solvent is
8 used for the isolation of 3-HBA in other cell-free biosynthetic cascades.²² To
9 evaluate the recyclability of this ethyl acetate, we decided to isolate the 3-HBA
10 produced from ethanol using ethyl acetate. Then, the solvent was evaporated and
11 reused as the starting material to again produce 3-HBA. Remarkably, HB-5.2
12 produced 5.45 mM of 3-HBA from 50 mM of recycled ethyl acetate (**Figure 6A**).
13 This titer was similar to that achieved with fresh ethyl acetate, demonstrating the
14 capacity of this heterogeneous biocatalyst to upcycle post-used ethyl acetate in
15 downstream processing. The use of biocatalysis to upcycle solvents is rare, yet
16 some examples have been reported to valorize green solvents like cyrene and
17 racemic ethyl glyceryl ether into pharmaceutical precursors.^{50, 82} Here, we add
18 one more example to this collection, valorizing the widely used ethyl acetate into
19 an enantiomerically pure 3-HBA. Additionally, we also tested bioethanol derived
20 from agricultural waste as a starting material (>99.5% purity with traces of
21 superior alcohols). Using 200 mM of this bio-based substrate, we produced
22 18.8 ± 2.1 mM of 3-HBA, a similar titer to that obtained with pure ethanol (**Figure**
23 **6A**).

24 Next, we tested HB-5.2 with primary diols, such as ethylene glycol, which
25 can potentially be obtained from the depolymerization of plastic waste (i.e, post-
26 consumer poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET)).^{83, 84} Starting from a mix of 180 mM
27 ethylene glycol and 20 mM ethanol, we analyzed the reaction crude by UPLC-
28 MS. We achieved 101 ± 66 μ M of a dihydroxybutanoic acid and 5.26 ± 0.74 μ M of
29 2,3,4-trihydroxybutanoic acid. Besides these polyhydroxy acids, we also found
30 557 ± 69 μ M 3-HBA, 11.9 ± 0.4 mM acetate, and 5.1 ± 0.8 mM 2-hydroxy acetic
31 (glycolic) acid (**Figure 6B and Figure S16-S17**) as byproducts. Using UPLC-MS,
32 we were unable to distinguish between the linear 3,4-dihydroxybutanoic acid and
33 the α -branched 2,3-dihydroxybutanoic acid, as both showed identical retention
34 times and masses. However, GC-MS analysis revealed a chromatographic peak
35 with the same retention time and mass fragmentation pattern as the 3,4-
36 dihydroxybutyric acid standard. No signal matching the 2,3-dihydroxybutyric acid
37 standard was detected (**Figure S18**), suggesting that the linear isomer was the
38 predominant product. These results indicate that HB-5.2 can condense,
39 asymmetrically reduce, and hydrolyze either two glycolyl-CoAs to yield an α, β, ω -
40 trihydroxylated acid or one glycolyl-CoA and one acetyl-CoA to produce the linear
41 β, ω -dihydroxylated acid. Based on GC-MS data, the branched condensation of
42 acetyl-CoA and glycolyl-CoA appears to be disfavored when catalyzed by HB-
43 5.2.

1
2 **Figure 6.** A) 3-HBA (purple) and acetate (grey) titers from different starting materials using HB-5.2 as
3 biocatalyst. *Recycled ethyl acetate from product purification. #Advanced bioethanol from biomass. All
4 starting materials were added to a final initial concentration of 50 mM plus 75 mM acetone, except bioethanol,
5 which was added to a final concentration of 200 mM with 300 mM acetone. B) Biosynthesis of 3-hydroxy
6 acids starting from a mix of 180 mM ethylene glycol and 20 mM ethanol. C) Biosynthesis of 3-hydroxy acids
7 starting from a mix of 180 mM 1-propanol and 20 mM ethanol. For each reaction described in panels A-C,
8 40 mg of HB-5.2 were resuspended in the corresponding reaction mix at a ratio of 1:5 (w/v). Additionally, the
9 reactions starting from ethyl acetate also contained 5 mg of Novozyme 435. Reactions were carried out as
10 described in the Methods section. D) Batch reaction cycles for the biosynthesis of 3-HBA (purple squares)
11 and acetate (grey squares) with HB-5.2 from ethanol. Acetate/3-HBA molar ratio is represented in black
12 circles. Reactions were triggered by adding 1 mL of the reaction mixture with 200 mM ethanol and 300 mM
13 acetone to 200 mg of HB-5.2 and incubating for 8 hours at 30 °C and 800 rpm. E) Scheme of a continuous
14 flow reaction with PBR loaded with 1 gram of HB-5.2, together with the working conditions (left side) and the
15 titer of 3-HBA (purple) and acetate (grey), as a function of the time on the stream (right side).

16 To further explore substrate flexibility, HB-5.2 was also tested with a mixture
17 of 1-propanol and ethanol under the same conditions used for ethylene glycol. In
18 this reaction, we mainly found non-condensed oxidized products, achieving

1 1.2 ± 0.4 mM acetic acid and 91.3 ± 2.9 mM propanoic acid (**Figure S16**). In
2 addition, we identified two hydroxy acids by UPLC-MS (**Figures 6C and S19**).
3 On one hand, we found 3-hydroxypentanoic acid (1.42 ± 0.48 mM) as the major
4 condensed product resulting from the linear condensation of propionyl-CoA and
5 acetyl-CoA in that order. On the other hand, a much lower amount of 2-methyl-3-
6 hydroxypentanoic acid (5.46 ± 3.4 μM) was found. This latter product was
7 synthesized through the branched condensation of two propionyl-CoA molecules.
8 Surprisingly, neither 3-HBA nor 2-methyl-3-hydroxybutyric acid were detected,
9 which suggests that ReTHL preferentially binds propionyl-CoA as a priming unit.
10 Once the enzyme is primed, it can condense either an acetyl-CoA or a second
11 propionyl-CoA. The product distribution observed with the ethanol/propanol
12 mixture is consistent with the behavior of HB-5.2 in reactions using
13 ethanol/ethylene glycol mix, where branched products were also limited. This is
14 likely due to the low ethanol concentration in the reaction mix, which restricts
15 acetyl-CoA availability. Acetyl-CoA is essential for initiating branched
16 condensation. Therefore, the low ethanol levels relative to 1-propanol or ethylene
17 glycol may explain the absence of branched products. Furthermore, branched
18 product formation may also be limited by ReTHL's inherent preference for linear
19 acyl-CoA condensation, consistent with previous *in vivo* observations^{80, 85}

20 To the best of our knowledge, none of these 3-hydroxy acids have ever been
21 synthesized from primary alcohols. This new biosynthetic pathway, enabled by
22 HB-5.2, provides an alternative to engineered fermentative processes. It also
23 complements *in vitro* cascades producing 3-HBA from D-xylose,⁸⁶ glucose,^{17, 86}
24 or homoserine.⁸⁷ These results remark the industrial potential of this
25 heterogeneous biocatalyst for valorizing primary alcohols and ethyl esters,
26 common substances that are produced in the industry as wastes.^{83, 84, 88, 89}

27

28 **Operational stability of HB-5.2 and its implementation for the** 29 **continuous synthesis of 3-HBA**

30 Once the efficiency and the versatility of HB-5.2 are proven to produce
31 β-hydroxy acids, we evaluated its operational stability in both batch and packed-
32 bed (PBR) reactors. In batch discontinuous mode, we first performed a complete
33 reaction course to simultaneously monitor the production of 3-HBA and acetate.
34 **Figure S20A** shows that 3-HBA production is 2 times faster than acetate
35 accumulation according to the reaction kinetic constants (0.32 and 0.158 h⁻¹ for
36 3-HBA and acetate, respectively). After 24 hours of batch reaction, HB-5.2
37 produced 16 ± 0.165 mM 3-HBA and 26 ± 0.218 mM acetate. After the first 8 h of
38 reaction, the 3-HBA titer reached a plateau, selecting this reaction time to assess
39 the HB-5.2 operational stability in batch. The heterogeneous biocatalyst was
40 reused for 7 consecutive cycles of 8 hours, and both 3-HBA and acetate titers
41 were determined by HPLC. **Figure 6D** shows that HB-5.2 was stable for 3

1 consecutive cycles with negligible variations in 3-HBA titer. Afterwards, the titer
2 decayed to 7.5 mM after the 7th cycle.

3 In parallel to the batch reaction cycles, we studied the continuous operation
4 of HB-5.2 for the synthesis of 3-HBA. To do so, we packed 0.5 g of HB-5.2 in a
5 plug-flow column to set up a PBR. This PBR was operated at three different flow
6 rates: 100, 30, and 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$, in a decreasing flow rate ramp, feeding 300 mM
7 acetone, 200 mM ethanol, 0.5 mM CoA, 1 mM NAD^+ and 1 mM TCEP at pH 8
8 and 30 °C. As expected, the higher flow rate led to a decrease in the 3-HBA titer
9 but increased the space-time yield (STY) of the process (**Figure S20B**). At 10 μL
10 min^{-1} , we detected 13.85 ± 0.22 mM of 3-HBA synthesized at $1.21 \text{ g} \times \text{L}^{-1} \times \text{h}^{-1}$. In
11 contrast, when the flow rate increased 10 times, the 3-HBA titer decreased to
12 2.0 ± 0.095 mM, and the STY just increased up to $1.77 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$. When analyzing
13 the acetate:3-HBA molar ratio, we observed a decrease in that ratio at higher flow
14 rates, supporting the higher efficiency of ReTHL to condense acetyl-CoA than
15 that of EcTesB to hydrolyze it. Hence, this insight was confirmed both in batch
16 and flow reactors. From flow rate analysis, we selected 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ as the
17 condition with the better balance between titer and STY to evaluate the
18 operational stability of the HB-5.2 under continuous operation. To this aim, we
19 fabricated a PBR packed with 1 g of HB-5.2 and fed it with the reaction mix
20 described above. **Figure 6E** shows a stable titer at 20 mM 3-HB during the first
21 36 hours of reaction. The 3-HBA in the outcome solution was isolated by liquid-
22 liquid organic phase extraction, resulting in 56% 3-HBA isolated yield. 1H-NMR
23 of this isolated product confirmed the presence of both 3-HBA and acetic acid
24 (**Figure S21**). Then the titer steadily decreased, reaching 50% of the initial titer
25 (10 mM) after 573 hours. Outstandingly, the PBR containing 5 enzymes and
26 utilizing substoichiometric amounts of two cofactors (NAD^+ and CoA) operated
27 for almost 24 days. The high operational half-time of this 5-enzyme immobilized
28 system supports the potential of protein immobilization technologies for the
29 development of highly stable biocatalysts to accelerate complex biosynthetic
30 cascades. Notably, the acetone valve not only maintained redox balance to drive
31 the oxidative cascade but also enabled high 3-HBA titers in the oxygen-limited
32 PBR, due to its oxygen-independent mechanism. The STY surpasses previously
33 reported five-enzyme oxidative cascades in PBRs that rely on enzyme-driven
34 H_2O_2 disproportionation for oxygen supply.³⁵ Unlike those systems, which show
35 operational lifetimes under 24 hours, the absence of H_2O_2 in our setup
36 contributes to its long-term stability, maintaining over 50% activity after three
37 weeks. All in all, HB-5.2 enables efficient oxidative cascades under limited oxygen
38 concentration, increasing the system's safety as high pressure to increase
39 oxygen supply is not needed, avoiding combustion risks.^{90, 91}

40 To further understand the PBR exhaustion, we interrogated HB-5.2 after its
41 use in both batch and PBR setups. To that aim, we performed ex-situ leaching
42 and kinetic studies of HB-5.2 after 7 batch cycles and 24 days of continuous

1 operation. For the PBR, we analyzed three main sections: inlet, medium, and
2 outlet, as previously described.⁴² Both protein loads and enzyme activity upon
3 operation were determined through SDS-PAGE analysis and enzyme activity
4 assays, respectively (**Figure S22**). On one hand, the SDS-PAGE showed some
5 leaching in the used HB-5.2, both under batch and flow conditions. Interestingly,
6 the enzyme leaching was more noticeable in the inlet section than in the middle
7 or outlet sections, though they were minimal. Specifically, the major loss of protein
8 occurred for Δ NPduP in the inlet section of the PBR reactor. We suggest that inlet
9 sections are subjected to higher operational stress (i.e., pressure drop),⁹²
10 facilitating the leaching of enzymes (or subunits) that are not fully irreversibly
11 bound. On the other hand, we observe no activity loss for immobilized BsADH,
12 TtHBDH, and EcTesB upon their use both in batch and flow setups. In contrast,
13 immobilized ReTHL maintained 75-60% of its initial activity after both continuous
14 and discontinuous operation. However, the most dramatic activity reduction was
15 observed in the immobilized Δ NPduP, which only retained 30% of its activity
16 before being used discontinuously in 7 batch cycles or continuously for 24 days
17 in the PBR, in agreement with the Δ NPduP leaching (**Figure S22**). Thus, the
18 operational inactivation of HB-5.2 is mainly due to Δ NPduP inactivation. Based
19 on these ex-situ experiments and the computational model, which predicts that
20 even minor losses of Δ NPduP activity strongly reduce 3-HBA titers, we suggest
21 that the bioreactor is primarily inactivated due to Δ NPduP. This enzyme is leached
22 and also likely loses function, probably because operational conditions induce
23 structural distortions. Post-immobilization polymer coatings may increase the
24 stability of the immobilized enzymes as seen in other works.⁴⁰

25 **Conclusions**

26 In this work, we have developed an in vitro enzymatic cascade with exceptionally
27 high theoretical mass yield (113 %)—surpassing other previously described
28 routes starting from glucose (58%) or vinyl acetate (60%) (**Table 1**). However,
29 this synthetic pathway faces a significant thermodynamic challenge as the
30 oxidative condensation of ethanol is 14 and 9 times less exergonic than in vitro
31 pathways starting from vinyl acetate and glucose, respectively (**Table 1**). Using a
32 cell-free and confined (immobilized) pathway, we surpassed the thermodynamic
33 limitations and produced (*S*)-3-HBA from ethanol. As a result, we achieved titers
34 comparable to those obtained from glucose, using both in vitro and in vivo
35 systems, and from vinyl esters in vitro. Although the titer is one order of magnitude
36 lower than that achieved for (*R*)-3-HBA via fed-batch fermentation from glucose,
37 these results highlight the strong potential of our approach. In contrast, when
38 starting from ethanol, our in vitro immobilized pathway produces a titer 18 times
39 higher than that obtained with *S. cerevisiae* engineered to synthesize 3-HBA via
40 a reverse fermentative pathway, despite being 21 times less favorable
41 thermodynamically than the corresponding pathway in this microorganism (**Table**
42 **1**).

1 **Table 1. Metrics comparison of different 3-HBA producing systems, including this work**

Ref.	System	Substrate	Isomer	ΔG° (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Theoretical Mass yield (%) ^[a]	Titer g L ⁻¹ (mM)	Yield (%) ^[b]	TTN _{CoA}	TTN _{NAD(H)}
5	In vivo (<i>E. coli</i>)	Glucose	R	-54	58	16.3 (157)	17.6	N.D.	N.D.
3	In vivo (<i>E. coli</i>)	Glucose	S	-54	58	2.08 (20)	53.6	N.D.	N.D.
19	In vivo (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	Ethanol	S	-133	113	0.1 (1)	2.2	N.D.	N.D.
28	Cell-free	Glucose	-	-54	58	1.35 (7)	-	5	2.5
22	Cell-free	Vinyl acetate	S	-88	60	2.5 (24)	24	9.6	9.6
This work	Immobilized	Ethanol	S	-6	112	1.87 (18)	18.8	72	72

[a] The theoretical mass yield is calculated considering the reaction stoichiometry without auxiliary co-substrates to keep the redox balance and assuming a 100% transformation efficiency of the substrate into 3-HBA without formation of by-products. [b] The yield is defined as the percentage of 3-HB produced regarding the initial concentration of feedstock (ethanol, glucose, or vinyl acetate), accounting for the reaction stoichiometry. 1 molecule of 3-HBA per 1 molecule of glucose, and per 2 molecules of either vinyl acetate or ethanol.

2

3 Despite the unfavorable thermodynamics, the high titers and yields we report in
4 this work were possible through a holistic biocatalyst engineering strategy.
5 Without such an engineering effort, this cell-free biosynthetic pathway fails to
6 efficiently transform ethanol into 3-HBA. Thus, enzyme co-immobilization
7 significantly enhanced operational stability and allowed the process
8 intensification in continuous reactors, achieving an unprecedented lifetime for
9 systems of such complexity. Furthermore, this system is flexible enough to
10 efficiently use different ethanol sources, including renewable ethanol and ethyl
11 and vinyl esters. Similarly, this heterogeneous biocatalytic system condenses
12 bulkier alcohols than ethanol, bearing C2 substitutions (i.e., -OH or -CH₃), which
13 enables access to dihydroxy, trihydroxy, and α -branched β -hydroxy acids via an
14 unprecedented route. As far as we know, there is only one precedent of a 5-
15 enzyme system co-immobilized on porous carriers and implemented in flow.⁴⁰
16 However, such a system is only a modification route to regioselectively oxidize
17 diols into γ -hydroxy acids, unlike the anabolic route herein described. Assembling
18 cell-free anabolic pathways utilizing multi-functional heterogeneous biocatalysts
19 is rarely exploited despite the advantages of spatially confining them. The multi-
20 functional heterogeneous biocatalyst herein developed yields some of the highest
21 total TTNs ever reported for in situ and simultaneous regeneration of two
22 cofactors (NAD(H) and CoA) (**Table 1**). Our results offer promising advances for

1 CoA-dependent pathway engineering, yet TTN values are still far from the
2 industrial requirements for expensive cofactors (TTN > 1,000).⁹³

3 Additionally, the immobilized enzyme system demonstrated great versatility in the
4 oxidative acylation of primary alcohols, yielding a variety of acyl-CoA derivatives.
5 These molecules have wide-ranging applications in chemical biology, serving as
6 substrates to probe unknown enzymatic activities or as precursors for the design
7 of novel in vitro biosynthetic pathways.⁹⁴⁻⁹⁶ Taken together, this study lays the
8 groundwork for the intensification of in vitro cascade reactions using immobilized
9 enzyme systems to transform simple, low-cost, and sustainable feedstocks into
10 high-value products. We envision expanding this concept to more complex
11 biosynthetic routes toward the synthesis of natural products.

12 **Methods**

13 **Materials**

14 Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotides (NAD⁺, NADH, NADP⁺ and NADPH)
15 were purchased from Gerbu Biotechnik GmbH (Heidelberg, Germany). Agarose
16 6% crosslinked beads (6BCL) were purchased from Agarose Beads Technologies
17 (Madrid, Spain). Primary alcohols (**1a-r**), coenzyme A derivatives (coenzyme A,
18 acetyl-CoA, propionyl-CoA and 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA), DL-dithiothreitol (DTT),
19 tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine (TCEP), Ellman's reagent (DTNB), alcohol
20 dehydrogenase from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (ScADH), (*R*)-3-hydroxybutyric
21 acid, 3-hydroxy-2-methylbutyric acid, (*S*)-3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid, (*2R,3R*)-
22 2,3,4-trihydroxybutyric acid, glycidol, sodium borohydride, iminodiacetic acid,
23 sodium periodate, kanamycin sulfate, IPTG, polyallylamine (Mw 65,000; PAH),
24 polyethyleneimine (Mw 60,000; PEI), cobalt (II) chloride and ethyl acetoacetate
25 were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co (St. Louis, IL, USA). Aldehydes (**2a-m**)
26 were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co (St. Louis, IL, USA) at a >95% purity and
27 stored as indicated by the manufacturer. 3-hydroxypentanoic acid and 3-hydroxy-
28 2-methylpentanoic acid were purchased from Biosynth (Berkshire, UK). 2,3-
29 dihydroxybutyric acid was purchased from Ambinter (Orleans, France).
30 Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC), rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RhB), atto 390
31 NHS ester, alexa fluor 647 NHS ester, Phusion High Fidelity DNA polymerase,
32 and FastDigest enzymes were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific
33 (Waltham, MA, USA). LB media, tryptone, and yeast extract were purchased from
34 NZYtech (Lisboa, Portugal). Protein concentrations were determined using the
35 Bradford Assay Kit from Bio-Rad (Hercules, CA, USA). SePduP (aldehyde CoA-
36 acylating dehydrogenase from *Salmonella enterica*), AsTHL5 (thiolase 5 from
37 *Ascaris suum*), ReTHL (thiolase from *Ralstonia eutropha*), EcTesB (thioesterase
38 B from *Escherichia coli*), BsADH (alcohol dehydrogenase from *Bacillus*
39 *stearothermophilus*), and LpNOX (NADH oxidase from *Lactobacillus pentosus*)
40 encoding sequences were optimized for *E. coli* codon usage, synthesized, and
41 cloned into the expression vector pET28b by Genscript (Leiden, Netherlands).

1 pET28b containing the coding sequences for TtHBDH (3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA
2 dehydrogenase from *Thermus thermophilus* HB27) was kindly donated by Prof.
3 J. Berenguer from Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain). pET28b containing
4 the coding sequences for BsGDH (glucose dehydrogenase from *Bacillus subtilis*)
5 was kindly donated by CASCAT GmbH (Straubing, Germany). All protein
6 sequences are provided in **Table S2**. *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) DH5 α and
7 BL21(DE3) strains from our collection were used to prepare chemically
8 competent bacteria for DNA propagation and protein expression, respectively.
9 Buffers and other reagents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Co. (St. Louis, IL,
10 USA). Advanced ethanol (EN 15376) was kindly provided by PERSEO
11 Biotechnology (Valencia, Spain). Solvents were purchased from Scharlab
12 (Barcelona, Spain).

13 **Deletion of N-terminal from pduP gene:**

14 Deletion of the first 28 amino acids of the SePduP was done through a PCR
15 strategy using Δ NPduP_fw and Δ NPduP_rv primers (**Table S1**). The thermal
16 cycle was configured like this: 30 s at 98 °C, the amplification of the Δ NPduP
17 gene was done for 35 cycles (15 s at 98 °C; 30 s at 67.4 °C and 1 min at 72 °C),
18 then 10 min at 72 °C. The amplicon was isolated using gel electrophoresis and
19 recloned into an empty pET28b(+) plasmid between the NdeI and BamHI
20 restriction sites and sequenced by Sanger sequencing using the T7 primers.

21

22 **Protein expression and purification**

23 Briefly, all the enzymes were transformed by thermal shock in *E. coli* BL21
24 cells with the corresponding plasmid, and they were grown overnight in lysogenic
25 broth (LB) agar plates supplemented with 50 μ g mL⁻¹ of kanamycin. Single
26 colonies from agar plates were picked and cultured in LB-kanamycin and 0.2%
27 glucose at 37 °C and 200 rpm shaking overnight. These growth cultures were
28 used for inoculating (1%) fresh media. All enzymes were expressed and purified
29 following standard methods (See supplementary methods).

30 **Enzymatic activity assays**

31 All enzymatic assays were carried out in a final volume of 200 μ L on a 96-well
32 plate in a Biotek Epoch2 Microplate Spectrophotometer thermostated at 30 °C.
33 The assays were triggered by adding 5 μ L of either a solution (free enzymes) or
34 a suspension (immobilized enzymes) with a known protein concentration to
35 calculate the specific (U/mg) and volumetric (U mL⁻¹) activities. 1 enzyme unit (U)
36 is specifically defined for each enzyme. Each enzyme was measured with an
37 specific activity assay as described in the supplementary methods. Specifically,
38 Δ NPduP was biochemically characterized (substrate scope, kinetic parameters
39 and pH profile) as described in supplementary methods.

1 **Enzyme immobilization**

2 Carrier functionalization was performed as previously described in a ratio of 1/10
3 (w/v) unless otherwise indicated.⁷⁴ Incubations were under mechanical stirring at
4 200 rpm at room temperature. Carrier recovery and washes were by vacuum
5 filtering. After its preparation, every carrier was stored at 4 °C.

6 Enzyme immobilization on glyoxyl agarose (AG-G): 100 mg of AG-G was
7 resuspended in 1 mL of a solution containing 1 U of the corresponding enzyme
8 in 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer at pH 10 and incubated for 1 to 3 hours at 4
9 °C or 25 °C. Then, 1 mg of NaBH₄ was added and incubated for 30 min. Finally,
10 the heterogeneous biocatalyst was washed with an excess of 0.1 M sodium
11 phosphate buffer at pH 7.

12 Enzyme immobilization on cobalt chelates agarose (AG-Co²⁺): 100 mg of AG-
13 Co²⁺ was resuspended in 1 mL of a solution containing 1 U of the corresponding
14 enzyme in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7.4 and incubated for 1 hour at
15 25 °C. When using crude extracts, the ratio between AG-Co²⁺ and crude extracts
16 never exceeded 1:20 (w/v).

17 Enzyme immobilization on polyethyleneimine/Polyallylamine agarose (AG-
18 PEI/PAH): 100 mg of AG-PEI or AG-PAH was resuspended in 1 mL of a solution
19 containing 1 U of the corresponding enzyme in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer
20 at pH 7, and incubated for 1 hour at 25 °C.

21 Enzyme immobilization on trifunctional agarose (AG-Co²⁺/G/A): 100 mg of AG-
22 Co²⁺/G/A was resuspended in 1 mL of a solution containing 1 U of the
23 corresponding enzyme in 200 mM NaCl, 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8,
24 and incubated for 1.5 hours at 25 °C. Then, 1 mg of NaBH₄ was added and
25 incubated for 30 min. Finally, the biocatalyst was washed with an excess of 0.1
26 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.

27 Co-immobilization of the 5-enzyme system on glyoxyl agarose (AG-G): 400 mg
28 of AG-G was resuspended in 4 mL of precooled 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer
29 at pH 10, containing the corresponding amount of each enzyme (**Table S5**). The
30 suspension is incubated for 1 hour at 4 °C under gentle stirring before its
31 reduction with 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ of NaBH₄ for 30 min. Finally, the biocatalyst was
32 washed with an excess of 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 7.

33 Co-immobilization of the 5-enzyme system on cobalt chelates agarose (AG-
34 Co²⁺): 500 mg of AG-Co²⁺ was resuspended in 20 mL of a mix of crude extracts
35 containing the corresponding enzymes in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH
36 7.4 and incubated for 1 hour at 4 °C.

1 Chromatographic methodologies

2 Ultra-performance liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (UPLC-
3 MS): NAD(H), Coenzyme A, and its thioester derivatives were analyzed and
4 quantified using an Acquity UPLC equipped with a photodiode array detector
5 (PDA) and coupled to an electrospray ionization and a time-of-flight mass
6 spectrometer (ESI-TOF) LCT Premier XE from Waters as described before.^{22, 74}
7 The chromatography was performed using an Acquity Premier BEH C18 2.1 x
8 100 mm, 1.7 μm column (Waters, MA, USA). The column was thermostated at
9 30 °C. The gradient elution buffers were (A) 100 mM ammonium formate in water
10 and (B) acetonitrile. The following gradient program was used at a 0.3 mL min⁻¹:
11 from 0 to 1 min, isocratic at 99% A; from 1 to 14 min, gradient to 80% A; from 14
12 to 15 min, gradient to 10% A; from 15 to 17 min, isocratic at 10% A; from 17 to
13 17.5 min, gradient back to 99% A; from 17.5 to 20 min, stabilization at 99% A. 5
14 μL of samples were injected and the quantification done by UV absorbance at
15 254 nm and its molecular masses were confirmed by ESI-TOF MS. Mass
16 spectrometry detection was performed working in positive mode. The MS range
17 was between m/z 100 and 1000. The capillary and cone voltages were set at
18 3000 and 100 V, respectively. The desolvation gas temperature was 220 °C, and
19 the source temperature was 120 °C. The desolvation gas flow was set at 600 L
20 h⁻¹, and the cone gas flow was set at 50 L h⁻¹. Quantification and data analysis
21 were done in Masslynx version 4.1.

22 Calibration curves of redox cofactors and CoA-derivatives using pure standards
23 were used to quantify their concentration in the reaction. According to these
24 concentrations, we determined the analytical yields of the reactions as described
25 in the following equation:

$$26 \quad \text{Analytical yield (A. yield) (\%)} = ([P]_t / [S]_o) \times 100$$

27 Where $[S]_o$ is the sum of cofactor species ((CoA + Acyl-CoA) or (NADH + NAD⁺))
28 and $[P]_t$ is the concentration of each cofactor species (CoA, Acyl-CoA, NADH or
29 NAD⁺) at a given reaction time (t).

30 α and/or γ functionalized β -hydroxyacids were analyzed and quantified using
31 an Acquity UPLC coupled to a Synapt XS high-resolution time-of-flight (Q-ToF)
32 mass spectrometer S from Waters. For the analysis of 3-hydroxybutyric acid, 3-
33 hydroxypentanoic acid, 3-hydroxy-2-methylbutyric acid, 3-hydroxy-2-
34 methylpentanoic acid, 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid, and 2,3-dihydroxybutyric acid,
35 an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 2.1 x 50 mm, 1.7 μm column was used (Waters, MA,
36 USA). The C18 column was thermostated at 40 °C. The gradient elution buffers
37 were (A) 0.1% TFA in water and (B) acetonitrile. The following gradient program
38 was used at a 0.4 mL min⁻¹: from 0 to 0.5 min, isocratic at 99% A; from 0.5 to 7
39 min, gradient to 1% A; from 7 to 8 min, isocratic at 1% A; from 8 to 8.5 min,
40 gradient to 99% A; from 8.5 to 10 min, stabilization at 99% A. The analysis of
41 2,3,4-trihydroxypentanoic acid was performed with an Acquity Premier BEH

1 Amide 2.1 x 50 mm, 1.7 μm column (Waters, MA, USA). The amide column was
2 thermostated at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The gradient elution buffers were (A) 100 mM ammonium
3 formate in water and (B) acetonitrile. The following gradient program was used at
4 a 0.3 mL min^{-1} : from 0 to 0.5 min, isocratic at 10% A; from 0.5 to 2.5 min, gradient
5 to 60% A; from 2.5 to 3 min, isocratic at 60% A; from 3 to 3.7 min, gradient to 10%
6 A; from 3.7 to 5 min, stabilization at 10% A. In all cases, 1 μL of samples and
7 standards were injected, and the quantification was done by extracting the
8 corresponding m/z ion chromatogram. Mass spectrometry detection was
9 performed working in negative mode. The MS range was between m/z 50 and
10 800. The capillary and cone voltages were set at 1200 and 30 V, respectively.
11 The desolvation gas temperature was 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the source temperature was
12 130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The desolvation gas flow was set at 800 L h^{-1} , and the cone gas flow was
13 set at 50 L h^{-1} . To guarantee accurate mass, the instrument was tuned for m/z
14 554.2615 (Leu-Enk) to apply the mass correction every 0.5 seconds of the
15 acquisition. Quantification and data analysis were done in QuanLynx V4.2.

16 High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC): Carboxylic acids and β -
17 hydroxyacids were quantified by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
18 (HPLC) on an Agilent Infinity II 1260 with a PDA detector from Agilent (Santa
19 Clara, CA, USA) using a RezexTM ROA-Organic Acid H+ (8%) 300 x 7.8 mm
20 column from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). Elution of compounds was
21 performed at an isocratic flow of 0.5 mL min^{-1} with a mobile phase of 2.5 mM
22 sulphuric acid in nanopure water.

23 Gas Chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC-MS): Alcohols,
24 aldehydes, acetone, carboxylic acids and β -hydroxyacids (3-hydroxy butyric acid,
25 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid and 2,3-dihydroxybutyric acid) were quantified in an
26 Agilent 7820a System gas chromatographer equipped with an Agilent 5975C
27 Mass Selective Detector (GC-MS) operated with electron ionization source and
28 using a J&W DB-WAX column (30m x 0.25 mm x 25 μm), helium as carrier gas.
29 The temperature of the injector was 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the temperatures for the detector
30 were 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the MS source and MS quadrupole, respectively. The
31 separation of the compounds was carried out by following the temperature ramp:
32 initial temperature, 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, was held for 4 min, then the temperature was increased
33 up to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a rate of 20 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and maintained for 3 min. Post-run time was
34 3 minutes at 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. For the analysis, 1 μL of the samples was injected into the
35 inlet working at a split ratio of 20:1 and a constant flow of 0.7 mL min^{-1} , the MS
36 range was between m/z 20 to 200. The MSD was turned off during the elution of
37 the solvent (water) (from 5.2 min to 6.7 min).

38

1 **Biotransformations performed by soluble and immobilized systems:**

2 Propionaldehyde to Propionyl-CoA catalyzed by soluble enzymes: The reactions
3 were carried out in 500 μL of 10 mM propionaldehyde, 1 mM CoA, 0.1-2.5 mM
4 NAD^+ , 1 mM TCEP or DTT in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8, 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and
5 250 rpm for 16 hours. Reactions were triggered by addition of ΔNPduP to a final
6 activity of 0.01 U mL^{-1} . Reaction containing NOX-based regeneration system
7 additionally contained 0.15 mM FAD^+ and 0.01 U mL^{-1} LpNOX. The reactions
8 were stopped by filtration through a 10 kDa membrane and analyzed as indicated
9 previously.

10 Alcohols to Acyl-CoA catalyzed by a heterogeneous biocatalyst: 2 mg of HB-1.X
11 were placed in a 2 mL tube and the reactions triggered by the addition of 300 μL
12 of a mix containing 10 mM alcohol **1a-b**, 1 mM CoA, 0.1 mM NAD^+ , 1 mM TCEP
13 and 50 mM acetone in 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8. The reactions
14 were incubated at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 800 rpm for 16 hours. The reactions were stopped
15 by filtration and analyzed as indicated previously.

16 Ethanol to 3-hydroxybutyric acid catalyzed by free enzymes: The reactions were
17 carried out in 500 μL of 200 mM ethanol, 300 mM acetone, 0.5 mM CoA, 1 mM
18 NAD^+ , 1 mM TCEP, and the indicated amount of enzymes in 0.15 M sodium
19 phosphate buffer at pH 8, 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and 250 rpm for 16 hours. When BsGDH was
20 present, the reaction mix also contained 100 mM glucose instead acetone. The
21 reactions were stopped by filtration through a 10 kDa membrane and analyzed
22 as indicated previously. Upon optimization of the cell-free system, the amount of
23 enzymes added to the reaction media was modified to 1 U mL^{-1} of BsADH, 20 U
24 mL^{-1} of ΔNPduP , 0.25 U mL^{-1} of ReTHL, 2.5 U mL^{-1} of TtHBDH, and 0.1 U mL^{-1}
25 of EcTesB. Likewise, the initial concentration of Coenzyme A decreased to 0.5
26 mM, and the initial concentration of ethanol and acetone increased to 200 mM
27 and 300 mM, respectively.

28 Ethanol to 3-hydroxybutyric acid catalyzed by immobilized enzymes: An indicated
29 amount of heterogeneous biocatalyst was placed in a 2 mL tube, and the reaction
30 was triggered by the addition of the reaction mix to a final ratio of 1/5 (w/v). The
31 reaction mixture contained 50-200 mM ethanol, 100-300 mM acetone, 0.5-1 mM
32 CoA, 1 mM NAD^+ , 1 mM TCEP, in 0.15 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8, 30
33 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and 800 rpm for 16 hours. The reactions were stopped by filtration and
34 analyzed by chromatographic methods as previously described. Operational
35 stability of HB-5.2 was assayed by performing consecutive batch cycles of 8
36 hours at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 800 rpm, increasing the reaction volume. 200 mg of HB-5.2
37 were resuspended in 1 mL 200 mM ethanol, 0.5 mM CoA, 1 mM NAD^+ , 1 mM
38 TCEP, 300 mM acetone in 0.15 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8. Each reaction
39 cycle was stopped by filtration, and the supernatant analyzed as indicated
40 previously. Between cycles, the HB-5.2 was washed with 0.1 M sodium
41 phosphate buffer at pH 8 and stored at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

1 Substrate scope of the immobilized multi-enzyme system: Acetaldehyde, vinyl
2 acetate, pure ethyl acetate or recycled ethyl acetate, ethylene glycol, and 1-
3 propanol and industrial ethanol were tested as starting materials. Unless
4 otherwise indicated, 40 mg of HB-5.2 were placed in a 2 mL tube, and the reaction
5 was triggered by the addition of the reaction mix to a final ratio of 1/5 (w/v). The
6 reaction mixtures contained 50 mM of the corresponding substrate, 0.5 mM CoA,
7 1 mM NAD⁺, 1 mM TCEP, 300 mM acetone in 0.15 M sodium phosphate buffer
8 at pH 8, 30 °C, and 800 rpm for 16 hours. The reactions starting from ethyl acetate
9 additionally contained 5 mg of Novozyme 435. Alternatively, bioethanol was also
10 tested as a starting material under the same conditions but using 200 mM as the
11 initial substrate concentration. Additionally, ethylene glycol and 1-propanol were
12 tested as starting materials in a mix with ethanol (molar ratio 10:1) to a total
13 concentration of 200 mM of alcohols. The concentration of the other components
14 of the reaction media was the same as described previously. All the reactions
15 were stopped by filtration and analyzed as indicated previously.

16 Continuous conversion of ethanol to 3-hydroxybutyric acid in flow: To determine
17 the STY at different flow rates (100, 30, 10 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), 0.5 g of HB-5.2 was packed
18 in a column and the reaction triggered by pumping reaction mix consisting of 200
19 mM ethanol, 300 mM of acetone, 0.5 mM CoA, 1 mM NAD⁺, 1 mM TCEP in 0.15
20 M sodium phosphate buffer at pH 8 and 30 °C. Samples were withdrawn from the
21 elution and analyzed as indicated previously. To determine the operational
22 stability of HB-5.2 in flow, 1 g of HB-5.2 was packed in a column, and the reaction
23 was triggered as described previously. Samples were withdrawn from the outlet
24 of the reactor after different times on stream, and analyzed as indicated
25 previously. 3-HBA in the outlet samples was isolated by liquid-liquid extraction
26 and characterized by ¹H-NMR (see supplemental method for more details).

27 **Computational modeling**

28 Construction of the computational model and the related analysis were
29 conducted using CopasiUI version 4.40.⁹⁷ A fixed compartment was created, and
30 8 reaction equations were entered as displayed in **Table S6-7**. A semi-quantitative
31 kinetic model was constructed, as initial settings, k_{eq} values listed in **Table**
32 **S6** were calculated using eQuilibrator 3.0,⁹⁸ with pH set as 8, pMg = 2, and ionic
33 strength = 0.2 M. K_{m} values were either experimentally determined or obtained
34 from the BRENDA database (**Table S6**). Considering that EcTesB hydrolyzes
35 Acetyl-CoA nonspecifically during the reaction, a specific function was developed
36 based on the Henri-Michaelis-Menten equation.

37 For the first round of model fitting, Model 1.0 was constructed with initial
38 concentrations of ethanol, acetone, CoA, and NAD⁺ set as 200, 300, 1, and 1 mM,
39 respectively. In the model, V_{max} values for each enzyme were set to the same
40 numerical value, being 1 or 10 U mL⁻¹. During model fitting, V_{max} values of BsADH
41 for ethanol (**1a**) and acetone in our model constantly followed a fixed ratio of 1:0.7
42 based on the specific activity values of BsADH for each compound and

1 V_{\max} values of EcTesB for 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA (**5a**) and acetyl-CoA (**3a**) in our
2 model constantly followed a fixed ratio of 1:0.15 based on the specific activity
3 values of EcTesB for each compound. The result of the first round of model fitting
4 was Model 1.1 (**Table S8**). For the second round of model fitting, the same
5 procedure as the first round of model fitting but using the enzyme concentrations
6 resulted from the first round, the result of the second round of model fitting was
7 Model 1.2 (**Table S8**).

8 **Fluorescence microscopy**

9 Enzymes were labelled following standard protocols. Technical details about
10 enzyme labelling are described in supplementary methods.

11 Epifluorescence microscopy imaging: To monitor intraparticle NADH distribution
12 during the conversion of ethanol to 3-hydroxybutyric acid in heterogeneous
13 media, reaction samples (containing either HB-1.3-labeled + HB-4, or HB-5.1)
14 were withdrawn and placed onto 8-well μ -slides (Ibidi, Gräfelfing, Germany).
15 NADH autofluorescence was visualized using epifluorescence microscopy on a
16 ZEISS Axio Observer microscope (Carl Zeiss, Germany) equipped with a Colibri
17 5 LED excitation system. Excitation was set at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 385/30$ nm, and emission
18 was collected at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 445/50$ nm using a 49 DAPI filter (excitation at 395 nm). For
19 tracking of labeled HB-1.3, images were acquired in the red channel using
20 excitation at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 550/25$ nm and emission at $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 605/70$ nm with a 43 HE
21 DsRed filter set (beamsplitter at 570 nm). At least two representative images were
22 acquired at each time point using a 10 \times objective, and data from 8–10 beads per
23 condition were analyzed to determine the mean relative fluorescence units (RFU)
24 and standard deviation. Image acquisition and processing were performed using
25 ZEISS ZEN software and FIJI (ImageJ).

26 Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy Imaging: The localization and distribution
27 of fluorophore-labeled immobilized enzymes for the different distributions were
28 recorded with a Spectral ZEISS LSM 880 confocal microscope. Imaging was
29 performed using 20 \times (0.8 NA) and 40 \times (1.2 NA) objectives and different excitation
30 lasers, λ_{ex} : 405 nm for Atto 390, λ_{ex} : 488 nm for FITC, λ_{ex} : 561 nm for Rhodamine
31 B, and λ_{ex} : 633 nm for Alexa Fluor 647. All samples of each biocatalyst with the
32 fluorescently labeled immobilized enzyme were suspended in an 8-well chamber
33 slide (Ibidi) in a 1:200 (w:v) buffered suspension in 25 mM phosphate buffer at
34 pH 7. The resulting micrographs were analyzed with FIJI software to determine
35 the relative infiltration radius and the colocalization parameters.^{40, 51, 99}

36

37 **Data availability.**

38 All data generated in this study are available in the Supplementary Information
39 and from the corresponding author upon request. Source data are provided with
40 this paper.

1 **Author contributions**

2 F.L-G and A.H.O conceived the project. A.H.O, I.L.L., D. A-S performed most of
3 the experiments. M.I performed confocal fluorescence microscopy studies. U. F-
4 P performed chromatographic analysis. F.L-G and A.H.O evaluated the data and
5 wrote the original draft. All authors contributed to the revision of the paper.

6 **Competing interests**

7 All authors declare no competing interests. CIC biomaGUNE has filed a
8 European patent (P6955EP00) on the fabrication of biocatalysts to transform
9 primary alcohols into β -hydroxy acids.

10 **Correspondence and requests for materials** should be addressed to Fernando
11 López-Gallego (flopez@cicbiomagune.es) and Alejandro H. Orrego
12 (aherrera@cicbiomagune.es).

13 **Keywords:** enzyme immobilization, thiolases, dehydrogenases, cell-free
14 metabolic engineering, biorefinery, biocatalysis.

15 **Supporting information**

16 Supplementary information contains primary sequences of enzymes, primers
17 used in this study, technical details of all heterogeneous biocatalysts herein
18 described, HPLC, UPLC-MS, and GC-MS information, ¹H-NMR of the isolated
19 products, and additional supporting experimental data.

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30 **References**

- 31 (1) Patel, R. N. Biocatalysis for synthesis of pharmaceuticals. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* **2018**, *26* (7), 1252-1274.
32 DOI: 10.1016/j.bmc.2017.05.023.
- 33 (2) de María, P.; de Gonzalo, G.; Alcántara, A. Biocatalysis as Useful Tool in Asymmetric Synthesis: An
34 Assessment of Recently Granted Patents (2014–2019). *Catalysts* **2019**, *9* (10). DOI: 10.3390/catal9100802.
- 35 (3) Tseng, H.-C.; Martin, C. H.; Nielsen, D. R.; Prather, K. L. J. Metabolic engineering of *Escherichia coli* for
36 enhanced production of (R)- and (S)-3-hydroxybutyrate. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2009**, *75* (10), 3137-3145.
37 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02667-08>.
- 38 (4) Chen, G.-Q.; Wu, Q. Microbial production and applications of chiral hydroxyalkanoates. *Appl. Microbiol.*
39 *Biotechnol.* **2005**, *67* (5), 592-599. DOI: 10.1007/s00253-005-1917-2.
- 40 (5) Perez-Zabaleta, M.; Guevara-Martínez, M.; Gustavsson, M.; Quillaguamán, J.; Larsson, G.; van Maris,
41 A. J. A. Comparison of engineered *Escherichia coli* AF1000 and BL21 strains for (R)-3-hydroxybutyrate

- 1 production in fed-batch cultivation. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2019**, *103* (14), 5627-5639. DOI:
2 10.1007/s00253-019-09876-y.
- 3 (6) Blaisse, M. R.; Dong, H.; Fu, B.; Chang, M. C. Y. Discovery and Engineering of Pathways for Production
4 of α -Branched Organic Acids. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, *139* (41), 14526-14532. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.7b07400.
- 5 (7) Schrittwieser, J. H.; Velikogne, S.; Kroutil, W. Artificial Biocatalytic Linear Cascades to Access Hydroxy
6 Acids, Lactones, and α - and β -Amino Acids. *Catalysts* **2018**, *8* (5), 205. DOI:
7 <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal8050205>.
- 8 (8) Park, H.; He, H.; Yan, X.; Liu, X.; Scrutton, N. S.; Chen, G.-Q. PHA is not just a bioplastic! *Biotechnol.*
9 *Adv.* **2024**, *71*, 108320. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2024.108320>.
- 10 (9) Tieu, K.; Perier, C.; Caspersen, C.; Teismann, P.; Wu, D.-C.; Yan, S.-D.; Naini, A.; Vila, M.; Jackson-
11 Lewis, V.; Ramasamy, R.; et al. D- β -Hydroxybutyrate rescues mitochondrial respiration and mitigates
12 features of Parkinson disease. *J. Clin. Invest.* **2003**, *112* (6), 892-901. DOI: 10.1172/JCI18797.
- 13 (10) Zhao, Y.; Zou, B.; Shi, Z.; Wu, Q.; Chen, G.-Q. The effect of 3-hydroxybutyrate on the in vitro
14 differentiation of murine osteoblast MC3T3-E1 and in vivo bone formation in ovariectomized rats.
15 *Biomaterials* **2007**, *28* (20), 3063-3073. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2007.03.003>.
- 16 (11) Yao, P.; Wang, L.; Yuan, J.; Cheng, L.; Jia, R.; Xie, M.; Feng, J.; Wang, M.; Wu, Q.; Zhu, D. Efficient
17 Biosynthesis of Ethyl (R)-3-Hydroxyglutarate through a One-Pot Biocatalytic Cascade of Halohydrin
18 Dehalogenase and Nitrilase. *ChemCatChem* **2015**, *7* (9), 1438-1444. DOI:
19 <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.201500061>.
- 20 (12) Lee, S.-H.; Park, S. J.; Lee, S. Y.; Hong, S. H. Biosynthesis of enantiopure (S)-3-hydroxybutyric acid in
21 metabolically engineered *Escherichia coli*. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2008**, *79* (4), 633-641. DOI:
22 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-008-1473-7>.
- 23 (13) Itsuno, S. Enantioselective Reduction of Ketones. In *Organic Reactions*, pp 395-576.
- 24 (14) Zhong, Z.; Ye, Y.; Zhang, Y.; Du, W.; Hou, Z. Alkali-Free Oxidation of 1,2-Propanediol to Lactic Acid over
25 Intermetallic Cu1Pt Compounds. *Langmuir* **2024**, *40* (49), 25882-25891. DOI:
26 10.1021/acs.langmuir.4c03138.
- 27 (15) Jablonski, P.; Irgum, K.; Mikkola, J.-P.; Wärnå, J.; Khokarale, S. G. Brønsted Acid Ionic Liquid Catalyzed
28 Depolymerization of Poly-(3-hydroxybutyrate) to 3-Hydroxybutyric Acid: Highly Selective and Sustainable
29 Transformation in Methyl Isobutyl Ketone and Water-Containing Phase-Separable Reaction Media. *ACS*
30 *Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2024**, *12* (37), 13946-13959. DOI: 10.1021/acssuschemeng.4c04723.
- 31 (16) Zhao, K.; Tian, G.; Zheng, Z.; Chen, J.-C.; Chen, G.-Q. Production of d(-)-3-hydroxyalkanoic acid by
32 recombinant *Escherichia coli*. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* **2003**, *218* (1), 59-64. DOI: 10.1111/j.1574-
33 6968.2003.tb11498.x.
- 34 (17) Martin, C. H.; Dhamankar, H.; Tseng, H.-C.; Sheppard, M. J.; Reisch, C. R.; Prather, K. L. A platform
35 pathway for production of 3-hydroxyacids provides a biosynthetic route to 3-hydroxy- γ -butyrolactone. *Nat.*
36 *Commun.* **2013**, *4* (1), 1-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms2418>.
- 37 (18) Keiser, L. S.; Gatenil, P. P.; Zhu, Y.; Deng, K.; Waldburger, L.; Gin, J. W.; Chen, Y.; Baidoo, E. E. K.;
38 Petzold, C. J.; Lanclos, N.; et al. Engineering Polyketide Stereocenters with Ketoreductase Domain
39 Exchanges. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2025**. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.5c06736.
- 40 (19) Yun, E. J.; Kwak, S.; Kim, S. R.; Park, Y.-C.; Jin, Y.-S.; Kim, K. H. Production of (S)-3-hydroxybutyrate
41 by metabolically engineered *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *J. Biotechnol.* **2015**, *209*, 23-30. DOI:
42 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2015.05.017>.
- 43 (20) Claassens, N. J.; Burgener, S.; Vögeli, B.; Erb, T. J.; Bar-Even, A. A critical comparison of cellular and
44 cell-free bioproduction systems. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **2019**, *60*, 221-229. DOI:
45 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2019.05.003>.
- 46 (21) Scheffen, M.; Marchal, D. G.; Beneyton, T.; Schuller, S. K.; Klose, M.; Diehl, C.; Lehmann, J.; Pfister,
47 P.; Carrillo, M.; He, H.; et al. A new-to-nature carboxylation module to improve natural and synthetic CO₂
48 fixation. *Nat. Catal.* **2021**, *4* (2), 105-115. DOI: 10.1038/s41929-020-00557-y.
- 49 (22) Orrego, A. H.; Rubanu, M. G.; López, I. L.; Andrés-Sanz, D.; García-Marquina, G.; Pieslinger, G. E.;
50 Salassa, L.; López-Gallego, F. ATP-Independent and Cell-Free Biosynthesis of β -Hydroxy Acids Using Vinyl
51 Esters as Smart Substrates. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62* (13), e202218312. DOI:
52 <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202218312>.
- 53 (23) Chen, K.; Arnold, F. H. Engineering new catalytic activities in enzymes. *Nat. Catal.* **2020**, *3* (3), 203-
54 213. DOI: 10.1038/s41929-019-0385-5.
- 55 (24) Emmanuel, M. A.; Bender, S. G.; Bilodeau, C.; Carceller, J. M.; DeHovitz, J. S.; Fu, H.; Liu, Y.; Nicholls,
56 B. T.; Ouyang, Y.; Page, C. G.; et al. Photobiocatalytic Strategies for Organic Synthesis. *Chem. Rev.* **2023**,
57 *123* (9), 5459-5520. DOI: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00767.
- 58 (25) Rasor, B. J.; Vögeli, B.; Landwehr, G. M.; Bogart, J. W.; Karim, A. S.; Jewett, M. C. Toward sustainable,
59 cell-free biomanufacturing. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **2021**, *69*, 136-144. DOI:
60 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2020.12.012>.
- 61 (26) Opgenorth, P. H.; Korman, T. P.; Bowie, J. U. A synthetic biochemistry module for production of bio-
62 based chemicals from glucose. *Nat. Chem. Biol.* **2016**, *12* (6), 393-395. DOI: 10.1038/nchembio.2062.
- 63 (27) Li, F.; Wei, X.; Zhang, L.; Liu, C.; You, C.; Zhu, Z. Installing a Green Engine To Drive an Enzyme
64 Cascade: A Light-Powered In Vitro Biosystem for Poly (3-hydroxybutyrate) Synthesis. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*
65 **2022**, *134* (1), e202111054. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202111054>.

- 1 (28) Karim, A. S.; Dudley, Q. M.; Juminaga, A.; Yuan, Y.; Crowe, S. A.; Heggstad, J. T.; Garg, S.; Abdalla,
2 T.; Grubbe, W. S.; Rasor, B. J.; et al. In vitro prototyping and rapid optimization of biosynthetic enzymes for
3 cell design. *Nat. Chem. Biol.* **2020**, *16* (8), 912-919. DOI: 10.1038/s41589-020-0559-0.
- 4 (29) Thompson, S.; Mayerl, F.; Peoples, O. P.; Masamune, S.; Sinskey, A. J.; Walsh, C. T. Mechanistic
5 studies on β -ketoacyl thiolase from *Zoogloea ramigera*: identification of the active-site nucleophile as
6 Cys89, its mutation to Ser89, and kinetic and thermodynamic characterization of wild-type and mutant
7 enzymes. *Biochem.* **1989**, *28* (14), 5735-5742. DOI: 10.1021/bi00440a006.
- 8 (30) Liu, H.; Arbing, M. A.; Bowie, J. U. Expanding the use of ethanol as a feedstock for cell-free synthetic
9 biochemistry by implementing acetyl-CoA and ATP generating pathways. *Sci. Rep.* **2022**, *12* (1), 7700. DOI:
10 10.1038/s41598-022-11653-3.
- 11 (31) Muñoz-Sánchez, D.; Carceller, A.; Álvaro, G.; Romero, O.; Guillén, M. Artificial cell-free system for the
12 sustainable production of acetoin from bioethanol. *Bioresour. Technol.* **2025**, *419*, 132059. DOI:
13 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2025.132059>.
- 14 (32) Velasco-Lozano, S.; Santiago-Arcos, J.; Grazia Rubanu, M.; López-Gallego, F. Cell-Free Biosynthesis
15 of ω -Hydroxy Acids Boosted by a Synergistic Combination of Alcohol Dehydrogenases. *ChemSusChem*
16 **2022**, *15* (9), Article. DOI: 10.1002/cssc.202200397.
- 17 (33) Velasco-Lozano, S.; Santiago-Arcos, J.; Mayoral, J. A.; López-Gallego, F. Co-immobilization and
18 Colocalization of Multi-Enzyme Systems for the Cell-Free Biosynthesis of Aminoalcohols. *ChemCatChem*
19 **2020**, *12* (11), 3030-3041. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.201902404>.
- 20 (34) Zeballos, N.; Diamanti, E.; Benitez-Mateos, A. I.; Schmidt-Dannert, C.; Lopez-Gallego, F. Solid-Phase
21 Assembly of Multienzyme Systems into Artificial Cellulosomes. *Bioconjugate Chem.* **2021**, *32* (9), 1966-
22 1972. DOI: 10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.1c00327.
- 23 (35) Karim, A. S.; Jewett, M. C. A cell-free framework for rapid biosynthetic pathway prototyping and enzyme
24 discovery. *Metab. Eng.* **2016**, *36*, 116-126. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2016.03.002>.
- 25 (36) Opgenorth, P. H.; Korman, T. P.; Bowie, J. U. A synthetic biochemistry molecular purge valve module
26 that maintains redox balance. *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, Article. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms5113.
- 27 (37) Kay, J. E.; Jewett, M. C. A cell-free system for production of 2,3-butanediol is robust to growth-toxic
28 compounds. *Metab. Eng. Commun.* **2020**, *10*, e00114. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mec.2019.e00114>.
- 29 (38) Khattak, W. A.; Ullah, M. W.; Ul-Islam, M.; Khan, S.; Kim, M.; Kim, Y.; Park, J. K. Developmental
30 strategies and regulation of cell-free enzyme system for ethanol production: a molecular prospective. *Appl.*
31 *Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **2014**, *98* (23), 9561-9578. DOI: 10.1007/s00253-014-6154-0.
- 32 (39) Xue, R.; Woodley, J. M. Process technology for multi-enzymatic reaction systems. *Bioresour. Technol.*
33 **2012**, *115*, 183-195. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2012.03.033>.
- 34 (40) Santiago-Arcos, J.; Velasco-Lozano, S.; Diamanti, E.; Benítez-Mateos, A. I.; Grajales-Hernández, D.;
35 Paradisi, F.; López-Gallego, F. Optimized Spatial Configuration of Heterogeneous Biocatalysts Maximizes
36 Cell-Free Biosynthesis of ω -Hydroxy and ω -Amino Acids. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2024**, *12* (25), 9474-
37 9489. DOI: 10.1021/acssuschemeng.4c02396.
- 38 (41) Bolivar, J. M.; Woodley, J. M.; Fernandez-Lafuente, R. Is enzyme immobilization a mature discipline?
39 Some critical considerations to capitalize on the benefits of immobilization. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2022**, *51* (15),
40 6251-6290. DOI: 10.1039/D2CS00083K.
- 41 (42) Andrés-Sanz, D.; Maiz-Iginitz, A.; Bolivar, J. M.; Orrego, A. H.; Sardon, H.; López-Gallego, F.
42 Enantiodivergent biosynthesis of β -hydroxy esters by self-sufficient heterogeneous biocatalysts in a
43 continuous flow. *Green Chem.* **2024**, *26* (8), 4563-4573. DOI: 10.1039/D4GC00369A.
- 44 (43) Benítez-Mateos, A. I.; Roura Padrosa, D.; Paradisi, F. Multistep enzyme cascades as a route towards
45 green and sustainable pharmaceutical syntheses. *Nat. Chem.* **2022**, *14* (5), 489-499. DOI: 10.1038/s41557-
46 022-00931-2.
- 47 (44) Altenburg, W. J.; Yewdall, N. A.; Vervoort, D. F. M.; van Stevendaal, M. H. M. E.; Mason, A. F.; van Hest,
48 J. C. M. Programmed spatial organization of biomacromolecules into discrete, coacervate-based protocells.
49 *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, *11* (1), 6282. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-20124-0.
- 50 (45) Liu, F.; Banta, S.; Chen, W. Functional assembly of a multi-enzyme methanol oxidation cascade on a
51 surface-displayed trifunctional scaffold for enhanced NADH production. *Chem. Commun.* **2013**, *49* (36),
52 3766-3768. DOI: 10.1039/C3CC40454D.
- 53 (46) Ellis, G. A.; Klein, W. P.; Lasarte-Aragonés, G.; Thakur, M.; Walper, S. A.; Medintz, I. L. Artificial
54 Multienzyme Scaffolds: Pursuing in Vitro Substrate Channeling with an Overview of Current Progress. *ACS*
55 *Catal.* **2019**, *9* (12), 10812-10869. DOI: 10.1021/acscatal.9b02413.
- 56 (47) Roberts, C. C.; Chang, C.-e. A. Modeling of Enhanced Catalysis in Multienzyme Nanostructures: Effect
57 of Molecular Scaffolds, Spatial Organization, and Concentration. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2015**, *11* (1),
58 286-292. DOI: 10.1021/ct5007482.
- 59 (48) Quin, M. B.; Wallin, K. K.; Zhang, G.; Schmidt-Dannert, C. Spatial organization of multi-enzyme
60 biocatalytic cascades. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2017**, *15* (20), 4260-4271. DOI: 10.1039/C7OB00391A.
- 61 (49) Diamanti, E.; Andrés-Sanz, D.; Orrego, A. H.; Carregal-Romero, S.; López-Gallego, F. Surpassing
62 Substrate-Enzyme Competition by Compartmentalization. *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13* (17), 11441-11454. DOI:
63 10.1021/acscatal.3c01965.
- 64 (50) Grajales-Hernández, D. A.; Diamanti, E.; Moro, R.; Velasco-Lozano, S.; Pires, E.; López-Gallego, F.
65 Spatial Organization of Immobilized Multienzyme Systems Improves the Deracemization of Alkyl Glyceryl
66 Ethers. *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13* (23), 15620-15632. DOI: 10.1021/acscatal.3c02615.

- (51) Diamanti, E.; Santiago-Arcos, J.; Grajales-Hernández, D.; Czarniewicz, N.; Comino, N.; Llarena, I.; Di Silvio, D.; Cortajarena, A. L.; López-Gallego, F. Intraparticle Kinetics Unveil Crowding and Enzyme Distribution Effects on the Performance of Cofactor-Dependent Heterogeneous Biocatalysts. *ACS Catal.* **2021**, *11* (24), 15051-15067. DOI: 10.1021/acscatal.1c03760.
- (52) Thorpe, T. W.; Marshall, J. R.; Turner, N. J. Multifunctional Biocatalysts for Organic Synthesis. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2024**, *146* (12), 7876-7884. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.3c09542.
- (53) Kong, W.; Huang, C.; Zhou, L.; Gao, J.; Ma, L.; Liu, Y.; Jiang, Y. Modularization of Immobilized Multienzyme Cascades for Continuous-Flow Enantioselective C–H Amination. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2024**, *63* (37), e202407778. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202407778>.
- (54) Bonfio, C.; Godino, E.; Corsini, M.; Fabrizi de Biani, F.; Guella, G.; Mansy, S. S. Prebiotic iron–sulfur peptide catalysts generate a pH gradient across model membranes of late protocells. *Nat. Catal.* **2018**, *1* (8), 616-623. DOI: 10.1038/s41929-018-0116-3.
- (55) Bobik, T. A.; Havemann, G. D.; Busch, R. J.; Williams, D. S.; Aldrich, H. C. The Propanediol Utilization (*pdu*) Operon of *Salmonella enterica* Serovar Typhimurium LT2 Includes Genes Necessary for Formation of Polyhedral Organelles Involved in Coenzyme B₁₂-Dependent 1,2-Propanediol Degradation. *J. Bacteriol.* **1999**, *181* (19), 5967-5975. DOI: doi:10.1128/jb.181.19.5967-5975.1999.
- (56) Lan, E. I.; Ro, S. Y.; Liao, J. C. Oxygen-tolerant coenzyme A-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase facilitates efficient photosynthetic n-butanol biosynthesis in cyanobacteria. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2013**, *6* (9), 2672-2681. DOI: 10.1039/C3EE41405A.
- (57) Fan, C.; Cheng, S.; Liu, Y.; Escobar, C. M.; Crowley, C. S.; Jefferson, R. E.; Yeates, T. O.; Bobik, T. A. Short N-terminal sequences package proteins into bacterial microcompartments. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **2010**, *107* (16), 7509-7514. DOI: doi:10.1073/pnas.0913199107.
- (58) Tobimatsu, T.; Kawata, M.; Toraya, T. The N-Terminal Regions of β and γ Subunits Lower the Solubility of Adenosylcobalamin-Dependent Diol Dehydratase. *Biosci., Biotechnol., Biochem.* **2005**, *69* (3), 455-462. DOI: 10.1271/bbb.69.455.
- (59) Shibata, N.; Tamagaki, H.; Hieda, N.; Akita, K.; Komori, H.; Shomura, Y.; Terawaki, S.-i.; Mori, K.; Yasuoka, N.; Higuchi, Y.; et al. Crystal Structures of Ethanolamine Ammonia-lyase Complexed with Coenzyme B₁₂ Analogs and Substrates. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2010**, *285* (34), 26484-26493. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M110.125112.
- (60) Kerfeld, C. A.; Erbilgin, O. Bacterial microcompartments and the modular construction of microbial metabolism. *Trends Microbiol.* **2015**, *23* (1), 22-34. DOI: 10.1016/j.tim.2014.10.003.
- (61) Yan, R. T.; Chen, J. S. Coenzyme A-acylating aldehyde dehydrogenase from *Clostridium beijerinckii* NRRL B592. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **1990**, *56* (9), 2591-2599. DOI: doi:10.1128/aem.56.9.2591-2599.1990.
- (62) Sánchez, L. B. Aldehyde Dehydrogenase (CoA-Acetylating) and the Mechanism of Ethanol Formation in the Amitochondriate Protist, *Giardia lamblia*. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics* **1998**, *354* (1), 57-64. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1006/abbi.1998.0664>.
- (63) Tsuji, K.; Yoon, K.-S.; Ogo, S. Biochemical characterization of a bifunctional acetaldehyde-alcohol dehydrogenase purified from a facultative anaerobic bacterium *Citrobacter* sp. S-77. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.* **2016**, *121* (3), 253-258. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiosc.2015.06.019>.
- (64) Palosaari, N. R.; Rogers, P. Purification and properties of the inducible coenzyme A-linked butyraldehyde dehydrogenase from *Clostridium acetobutylicum*. *J. Bacteriol.* **1988**, *170* (7), 2971-2976. DOI: doi:10.1128/jb.170.7.2971-2976.1988.
- (65) Getz, E. B.; Xiao, M.; Chakrabarty, T.; Cooke, R.; Selvin, P. R. A Comparison between the Sulfhydryl Reductants Tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine and Dithiothreitol for Use in Protein Biochemistry. *Anal. Biochem.* **1999**, *273* (1), 73-80. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1999.4203>.
- (66) Catalano, A.; Mariconda, A.; D'Amato, A.; Iacopetta, D.; Ceramella, J.; Marra, M.; Saturnino, C.; Sinicropi, M. S.; Longo, P. Aldehydes: What We Should Know About Them. *Organics* **2024**, *5* (4), 395-428. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/org5040021>.
- (67) Suchy, L.; Rudroff, F. In situ Generation of Aldehydes for Subsequent Biocatalytic Cascade Reactions in Whole Cells. *ChemCatChem* **2024**, *16* (2), e202301138. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.202301138>.
- (68) Smith, M. B. *March's advanced organic chemistry: reactions, mechanisms, and structure*; John Wiley & Sons, 2025. DOI: 10.1002/0470084960.
- (69) Flamholz, A.; Noor, E.; Bar-Even, A.; Milo, R. eQuilibrator—the biochemical thermodynamics calculator. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2011**, *40* (D1), D770-D775. DOI: 10.1093/nar/gkr874.
- (70) Guo, X.; Feng, Y.; Wang, X.; Liu, Y.; Liu, W.; Li, Q.; Wang, J.; Xue, S.; Zhao, Z. K. Characterization of the substrate scope of an alcohol dehydrogenase commonly used as methanol dehydrogenase. *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* **2019**, *29* (12), 1446-1449. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2019.04.025>.
- (71) Guagliardi, A.; Martino, M.; Iaccarino, I.; De Rosa, M.; Rossi, M.; Bartolucci, S. Purification and characterization of the alcohol dehydrogenase from a novel strain of *Bacillus stearothermophilus* growing at 70 degrees C. *Int. J. Biochem. Cell Biol.* **1996**, *28* (2), 239-246. DOI: 10.1016/1357-2725(95)00138-7.
- (72) Santiago-Arcos, J.; Velasco-Lozano, S.; López-Gallego, F. Multienzyme Coimmobilization on Triheterofunctional Supports. *Biomacromolecules* **2023**, *24* (2), 929-942. DOI: 10.1021/acs.biomac.2c01364.
- (73) Vázquez-Figueroa, E.; Chaparro-Riggers, J.; Bommaris, A. S. Development of a Thermostable Glucose Dehydrogenase by a Structure-Guided Consensus Concept. *ChemBioChem* **2007**, *8* (18), 2295-2301. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbic.200700500>.

- (74) López, I. L.; Sánchez-Costa, M.; Orrego, A. H.; Zeballos, N.; Roura Padrosa, D.; López-Gallego, F. Microtiter Plate Immobilization Screening for Prototyping Heterogeneous Enzyme Cascades. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2024**, *63* (35), e202407411. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202407411>.
- (75) Mateo, C.; Palomo, J. M.; Fuentes, M.; Betancor, L.; Grazu, V.; López-Gallego, F.; Pessela, B. C. C.; Hidalgo, A.; Fernández-Lorente, G.; Fernández-Lafuente, R.; et al. Glyoxyl agarose: A fully inert and hydrophilic support for immobilization and high stabilization of proteins. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* **2006**, *39* (2), 274-280. DOI: 10.1016/j.enzmictec.2005.10.014.
- (76) Fernandez-Lorente, G.; Lopez-Gallego, F.; M Bolivar, J.; Rocha-Martin, J.; Moreno-Perez, S.; M Guisan, J. Immobilization of proteins on highly activated glyoxyl supports: Dramatic increase of the enzyme stability via multipoint immobilization on pre-existing carriers. *Curr. Org. Chem.* **2015**, *19* (17), 1719-1731. DOI: 10.2174/138527281917150806125708.
- (77) Guisán, J. M. Aldehyde-agarose gels as activated supports for immobilization-stabilization of enzymes. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* **1988**, *10* (6), 375-382. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-0229\(88\)90018-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0141-0229(88)90018-X).
- (78) Wei, X.; Yang, X.; Hu, C.; Li, Q.; Liu, Q.; Wu, Y.; Xie, L.; Ning, X.; Li, F.; Cai, T.; et al. ATP-free in vitro biotransformation of starch-derived maltodextrin into poly-3-hydroxybutyrate via acetyl-CoA. *Nat. Commun.* **2024**, *15* (1), 3267. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-024-46871-y.
- (79) Siedentop, R.; Dziennus, M.; Lütz, S.; Rosenthal, K. Debottlenecking of an In Vitro Enzyme Cascade Using a Combined Model- and Experiment-Based Approach. *Chem. Ing. Tech.* **2023**, *95* (4), 543-548. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.202200170>.
- (80) Bonk, B. M.; Tarasova, Y.; Hicks, M. A.; Tidor, B.; Prather, K. L. J. Rational design of thiolase substrate specificity for metabolic engineering applications. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **2018**, *115* (9), 2167-2182. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.26737>.
- (81) Harijan, R. K.; Dalwani, S.; Kiema, T.-R.; Venkatesan, R.; Wierenga, R. K. Thiolase: A Versatile Biocatalyst Employing Coenzyme A–Thioester Chemistry for Making and Breaking C–C Bonds. *Annu. Rev. Biochem.* **2023**, *92* (Volume 92, 2023), 351-384. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biochem-052521-033746>.
- (82) Prier, C. K.; Camacho Soto, K.; Forstater, J. H.; Kuhl, N.; Kuethe, J. T.; Cheung-Lee, W. L.; Di Maso, M. J.; Eberle, C. M.; Grosser, S. T.; Ho, H.-I.; et al. Amination of a Green Solvent via Immobilized Biocatalysis for the Synthesis of Nemtabrutinib. *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13* (12), 7707-7714. DOI: 10.1021/acscatal.3c00941.
- (83) Pandit, A. V.; Srinivasan, S.; Mahadevan, R. Redesigning metabolism based on orthogonality principles. *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8* (1), 15188. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms15188.
- (84) Balola, A.; Ferreira, S.; Rocha, I. From plastic waste to bioprocesses: Using ethylene glycol from polyethylene terephthalate biodegradation to fuel *Escherichia coli* metabolism and produce value-added compounds. *Metab. Eng. Commun.* **2024**, *19*, e00254. DOI: 10.1016/j.mec.2024.e00254.
- (85) Dong, H.; Liffland, S.; Hillmyer, M. A.; Chang, M. C. Y. Engineering in Vivo Production of α -Branched Polyesters. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141* (42), 16877-16883. DOI: 10.1021/jacs.9b08585.
- (86) Wang, J.; Shen, X.; Jain, R.; Wang, J.; Yuan, Q.; Yan, Y. Establishing a novel biosynthetic pathway for the production of 3,4-dihydroxybutyric acid from xylose in *Escherichia coli*. *Metab. Eng.* **2017**, *41*, 39-45. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2017.03.003>.
- (87) Walther, T.; Calvayrac, F.; Malbert, Y.; Alkim, C.; Dressaire, C.; Cordier, H.; François, J. M. Construction of a synthetic metabolic pathway for the production of 2,4-dihydroxybutyric acid from homoserine. *Metab. Eng.* **2018**, *45*, 237-245. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2017.12.005>.
- (88) Mendoza-Pedroza, J. d. J.; Sánchez-Ramírez, E.; Segovia-Hernández, J. G.; Hernández, S.; Orjuela, A. Recovery of alcohol industry wastes: Revaluation of fusel oil through intensified processes. *CEP:PI* **2021**, *163*, 108329. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2021.108329>.
- (89) Meng, D.; Dai, Y.; Xu, Y.; Wu, Y.; Cui, P.; Zhu, Z.; Ma, Y.; Wang, Y. Energy, economic and environmental evaluations for the separation of ethyl acetate/ethanol/water mixture via distillation and pervaporation unit. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* **2020**, *140*, 14-25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2020.04.039>.
- (90) Hone, C. A.; Roberge, D. M.; Kappe, C. O. The Use of Molecular Oxygen in Pharmaceutical Manufacturing: Is Flow the Way to Go? *ChemSusChem* **2017**, *10* (1), 32-41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201601321>.
- (91) Hone, C. A.; Kappe, C. O. The Use of Molecular Oxygen for Liquid Phase Aerobic Oxidations in Continuous Flow. In *Accounts on Sustainable Flow Chemistry*, Noël, T., Luque, R. Eds.; Springer International Publishing, 2020; pp 67-110.
- (92) Zhao, D.; Zhao, M. On the Study of Packed Catalyst Bed Stresses for Outward Radial Flow Reactors. In *ASME 2020 Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference*, 2020; V003T03A036, Vol. Volume 3: Design and Analysis. DOI: 10.1115/pvp2020-21611.
- (93) Holtmann, D.; Fraaije, M. W.; Arends, I. W. C. E.; Opperman, D. J.; Hollmann, F. The taming of oxygen: biocatalytic oxygen functionalisations. *Chem. Commun.* **2014**, *50* (87), 13180-13200. DOI: 10.1039/C3CC49747J.
- (94) Ducrot, L.; López, I. L.; Orrego, A. H.; López-Gallego, F. Coenzyme A Thioester Intermediates as Platform Molecules in Cell-Free Chemical Biomanufacturing. *ChemBioChem* **2024**, *25* (2), e202300673. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbic.202300673>.
- (95) Walsh, C. T. Polyketide and Nonribosomal Peptide Antibiotics: Modularity and Versatility. *Science* **2004**, *303* (5665), 1805-1810. DOI: doi:10.1126/science.1094318.

- 1 (96) Schnepel, C.; Pérez, L. R.; Yu, Y.; Angelastro, A.; Heath, R. S.; Lubberink, M.; Falcioni, F.; Mulholland,
2 K.; Hayes, M. A.; Turner, N. J.; et al. Thioester-mediated biocatalytic amide bond synthesis with in situ thiol
3 recycling. *Nat. Catal.* **2023**, *6* (1), 89-99. DOI: 10.1038/s41929-022-00889-x.
- 4 (97) Hoops, S.; Sahle, S.; Gauges, R.; Lee, C.; Pahle, J.; Simus, N.; Singhal, M.; Xu, L.; Mendes, P.; Kummer,
5 U. COPASI—a COmplex PAtHway Simulator. *Bioinformatics* **2006**, *22* (24), 3067-3074. DOI:
6 10.1093/bioinformatics/btl485.
- 7 (98) Beber, M. E.; Gollub, M. G.; Mozaffari, D.; Shebek, K. M.; Flamholz, Avi I.; Milo, R.; Noor, E. eQuilibrator
8 3.0: a database solution for thermodynamic constant estimation. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2021**, *50* (D1), D603-
9 D609. DOI: 10.1093/nar/gkab1106.
- 10 (99) Schindelin, J.; Arganda-Carreras, I.; Frise, E.; Kaynig, V.; Longair, M.; Pietzsch, T.; Preibisch, S.;
11 Rueden, C.; Saalfeld, S.; Schmid, B.; et al. Fiji: an open-source platform for biological-image analysis. *Nat.*
12 *Methods* **2012**, *9* (7), 676-682. DOI: 10.1038/nmeth.2019.
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